

Research review paper

Implementing CRISPR-Cas technologies in conventional and non-conventional yeasts: Current state and future prospects

Hana Raschmanová^{a,1}, Astrid Weninger^{b,1}, Anton Glieder^b, Karin Kovar^c, Thomas Vogl^{d,*}^a Department of Biotechnology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Technická 5, 16628 Prague, Czech Republic^b Institute for Molecular Biotechnology, Graz University of Technology, NAWI Graz, Petersgasse 14, 8010 Graz, Austria^c Institute of Chemistry and Biotechnology, Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Grüentalstrasse 14, 8820 Wädenswil, Switzerland^d Department of Computer Science and Applied Mathematics, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot 76100, Israel

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ABSTRACT

Within five years, the CRISPR-Cas system has emerged as the dominating tool for genome engineering, while also changing the speed and efficiency of metabolic engineering in conventional (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*) and non-conventional (*Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Pichia pastoris syn. Komagataella phaffii*, *Kluyveromyces lactis*, *Candida albicans* and *C. glabrata*) yeasts.

Especially in *S. cerevisiae*, an extensive toolbox of advanced CRISPR-related applications has been established, including crisprTFs and gene drives. The comparison of innovative CRISPR-Cas expression strategies in yeasts presented here may also serve as guideline to implement and refine CRISPR-Cas systems for highly efficient genome editing in other eukaryotic organisms.

1. Introduction

Yeasts are widely used host organisms in biotechnology to produce biopharmaceuticals, industrial biocatalysts, food additives, fine chemicals and renewable biofuels (Kim et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2013; Martínez et al., 2012; Mattanovich et al., 2012; Radecka et al., 2015; Spencer et al., 2002; Wagner and Alper, 2015). As simple, unicellular eukaryotes, yeasts unify several key advantages of both bacteria and higher eukaryotes (e.g. mammalian cell lines) (Berlec and Strukelj, 2013; Demain and Vaishnav, 2009; Vogl et al., 2013; Walsh, 2010). Due to their robust physiology, yeasts are in contrast to mammalian cell lines well suitable for bioreactor cultivations and depending on the species even tolerating harsh growth conditions (i.e. elevated temperatures, organic solvents and low pH) (Radecka et al., 2015). At the same time, yeasts offer complex eukaryotic posttranslational modifications that are unobtainable in bacterial hosts (Vogl et al., 2013; Walsh, 2010) and often vital for producing biopharmaceuticals for human use. Compared to mammalian cell lines, yeasts are also more amenable to genetic modifications, although this aspect varies considerably between different species.

Saccharomyces cerevisiae (baker's yeast) has been used for millennia for baking and brewing and has for decades been established as a model

organism in biomedical research. Furthermore *S. cerevisiae* is also a popular host for metabolic engineering endeavours (Nevoigt, 2008) and the production of fine chemicals by the expression of heterologous biosynthetic pathways (Paddon et al., 2013). Also the fission yeast *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* is industrially used and has also become a model organism, as it is phylogenetically even closer related to higher eukaryotes than *S. cerevisiae* (Petrescu-Danila et al., 2009; Sambamurti, 1997).

In addition to these two long-known yeasts, currently more than 2,000 yeast species have been characterized (Radecka et al., 2015) and several non-conventional yeasts have increasingly been used for various biotechnological applications (Mattanovich et al., 2012; Radecka et al., 2015; Wagner and Alper, 2015). *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Komagataella phaffii* (*Pichia pastoris*), *Hansenula polymorpha* (*Ogataea angusta*), *Kluyveromyces lactis*, *Candida albicans* and *C. glabrata* are arguably amongst the most frequently used and well-studied non-conventional yeasts. The oleaginous yeast *Y. lipolytica* can utilize various unusual carbon sources (e.g. parraffins) to produce bio-renewable compounds (Ledesma-Amaro and Nicaud, 2016a). The methylotrophic yeasts *P. pastoris*, *H. polymorpha*, *Candida boidinii* and *Pichia methanolica* are widely used host platforms for heterologous protein production (Gellissen, 2000; Hartner and Glieder, 2006; Yurimoto et al., 2011). *P. pastoris* is the most

* Corresponding author at: Department of Computer Science and Applied Mathematics, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot 76100, Israel.

E-mail address: thomas.vogl@weizmann.ac.il (T. Vogl).

¹ These authors contributed equally.

commonly used methylotrophic yeast and according to a recent literature survey (Bill, 2014) even more frequently used for the production of single proteins than *S. cerevisiae*. *K. lactis* is typically used in food biotechnology (Rodicio and Heinisch, 2013; Spohner et al., 2016). However, non-conventional yeasts are also relevant for biomedical research: The facultative pathogenic species *C. albicans* and *C. glabrata* are frequent human commensals, but can cause serious infections, especially in immunocompromised individuals (Berman and Sudbery, 2002; Fidel et al., 1999; Kabir and Hussain, 2009).

In virtually all applications of these yeasts in current research and industry, genetic modifications are required to study gene functions as well as controlled insertions of expression cassettes to produce single proteins or entire metabolic pathways. Strain engineering for metabolic engineering endeavours also frequently requires the knockout or overexpression of the genes coding for certain enzymes to re-channel the metabolic flux towards a desired metabolite (Du et al., 2012; Stephanopoulos, 2012). Conventional approaches for genetic modifications of these yeasts relying on naturally occurring DNA repair mechanism have been in part limited by low efficiencies and complex knockout/insertion cassette designs (Section 1.1). The complex expression cassettes are undesirable particularly in the development of chassis strains for industrial applications, since these cassettes may introduce some unnecessary and/or concern-raising genetic elements (multiple cloning sites, bacterial origins of replication, drug resistant markers). As a versatile, highly efficient, marker-less and user-friendly method, the CRISPR-Cas system has become a revolutionary new approach to genome editing (Section 1.2). This review focusses on the implementation of CRISPR-Cas as a tool for genome engineering, metabolic engineering and/or regulation of transcription in conventional and non-conventional yeasts.

1.1. Genetic modifications relying on natural DNA repair

The natural amenability for achieving targeted genetic modifications varies greatly between organisms, depending on the preferred DNA repair pathway. Double stranded breaks (DSBs) in DNA can either be repaired by homologous recombination (HR) or non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) (Fig. 1) (Weninger et al., 2016b). In short, host mediated DNA repair via HR requires a homologous DNA template with sequence similarity to the damaged DNA (e.g. from a sister chromosome or an externally provided expression cassette flanked by homology arms). In contrast, NHEJ is a template independent closing of DSBs immediately by ligation. This can result in an unspecific (ectopic) integration of exogenous DNA into the genome (Fig. 1) and may lead to insertions and deletions (indels) in the process (Barnes, 2001; Capecchi, 1989; Dudás and Chovanec, 2004; Lieber, 2010).

Yeasts show a large variability in their preference for HR or NHEJ: In *S. cerevisiae* HR is the preferred pathway, resulting in close to 100% correct integration of exogenous DNA with short (~50 bp) homology arms. In contrast, for example in *P. pastoris* exogenous cassettes with long (~1 kbp) homology arms are integrated ectopically and HR occurs only at variable frequencies of < 0.1 to 30% (depending on the genomic site targeted and the length of the homology arms) (Näätsaari et al., 2012) (detailed information on HR and NHEJ in different yeast species is provided in Section 3 and Table 5). Conventional expression/knockout cassettes also require the insertion of selection markers (antibiotic resistance genes or auxotrophic markers) between the homology arms to select for genetic modifications. Such additional DNA elements can cause artifacts in molecular biological analyses by influencing their DNA neighbourhood and increase the complexity of legal approval of production strains. Especially, the deposit of the drug resistance gene can prevent the strain from a potential industrial application because of public health and safety concerns. Hence, strategies enabling marker-less modifications and higher rates of HR have been sought after.

1.2. CRISPR-Cas9 mediated genome editing

1.2.1. Function of Cas9 and gRNA

CRISPR-Cas9 is naturally a defence mechanism of bacteria and archaea providing adaptive immunity against invading DNA sequences (e.g. phages) (Barrangou, 2015; Deltcheva et al., 2011; Rath et al., 2015) and has been adapted for genome editing purposes. Most CRISPR-Cas9 systems for genome editing applications require only two components: 1.) a guide RNA (gRNA) complementary to the targeted region in the genome and 2.) an RNA guided DNA endonuclease (e.g. Cas9 or Cpf1 (Burstein et al., 2016; Zetsche et al., 2015)). The gRNA is bound by the endonuclease and targets the enzyme to the complementary DNA region resulting in double strand cleavage (Fig. 1). The DSB can, on the one hand, be repaired by NHEJ, which is prone to (indels). On the other hand, the DSB can also be repaired via HR if a donor cassette with homology arms is provided (Fig. 1). The rate of HR is in case of a targeted DSB in the genome generally greatly increased (up to 4000-fold) (Caldecott, 2008; Rouet et al., 1994; Smih et al., 1995; Storici et al., 2003). The key difference between natural occurring HR and CRISPR-Cas9 mediated HR is that natural HR repair relies on a strand break that occurs coincidentally at the target locus (by stress or during DNA replication (Segurado et al., 2002)), whereas a DSB is artificially created when using CRISPR-Cas9. CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing systems are already widely used in basic research and industry, although commercial applications are overshadowed by a patent dispute (Brinegar et al., 2017; Egelie et al., 2016; Ledford, 2017a, 2017b; Reardon, 2016).

A single stranded break (SSB, nick) in DNA is in cells precisely repaired by HR, not by NHEJ (Standage-Beier et al., 2015), which minimizes the mutagenic effects. Such nicks can be introduced by mutated Cas9 'nickase' variants (nCas9), whose endonuclease activity is converted to a nickase activity (Cong et al., 2013; Jinek et al., 2012). Two variants of the Cas9 nickase were designed; nCas9 D10A cleaves the gRNA-targeted strand, and nCas9 H840A cleaves the non-targeted strand (Standage-Beier et al., 2015). However, the HR-repair of nicks was reported to be less effective than the HR-repair of the DSBs in human cell cultures (McConnell Smith et al., 2009; Metzger et al., 2011) and *S. cerevisiae* (Satomura et al., 2017).

Cas9 was the first RNA guided DNA endonuclease reported in the literature, naturally requiring two RNA molecules serving as a guide (Jinek et al., 2012). Namely a CRISPR targeting RNA (crRNA) and a *trans*-activating crRNA (tracrRNA) need to bind to each other and then form a complex with Cas9. In follow up research, the crRNA and tracrRNA were merged, resulting in a single guide RNA (sgRNA) sufficient for targeting Cas9 (Jinek et al., 2012). The sgRNA consists therefore of a structural part and a variable 20 bp part that is adapted to match the genomic target sequence (Jinek et al., 2012; Mali et al., 2013).

Although alternative RNA guided endonucleases have been reported, Cas9 remains the most common enzyme and was used for nearly all genome editing applications in yeast discussed in this review (except for the very recent use of Cpf1 in *S. cerevisiae* (Swiat et al., 2017; Verwaal et al., 2017)). The RNA guided endonucleases of other CRISPR-Cas systems are, however, in part smaller than Cas9 and recognize different protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequences (a PAM is a short DNA sequence adjacent to the gRNA target and naturally helps bacteria to discriminate between targets in their own and invading DNA (Jinek et al., 2012; Sander and Joung, 2014)). Due to the possibility of precise and simple targeting of almost any sequence within a genome by a 20 nucleotide gRNA, CRISPR-Cas9 has revolutionized genome editing. The re-programming for new targets of comparable nucleases such as transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs) or ZFNs (zinc finger nucleases) is considerably more difficult, as the DNA binding domains of the proteins and not simply a short RNA need to be modified (Gasiunas and Siksnys, 2013). Furthermore, CRISPR-Cas9 can also be adapted for other applications such as regulating transcription

Fig. 1. Genetic modifications via naturally occurring and CRISPR-Cas9-promoted DNA repair mechanisms.

The genetic modifications based solely on the naturally occurring DNA repair mechanisms only involve the delivery of an exogenous targeting cassette with 5' and 3' homology arms (HAs) identical to the genome. The cassette can be integrated via two mechanisms: homologous recombination (HR), or non-homologous end joining (NHEJ). HR leads to specific integration via the HAs, NHEJ leads to integration in an arbitrary spot in the genome. The preference for HR or NHEJ can strongly vary between organisms (for yeasts, see Section 3, Table 5). The genetic modifications involving the CRISPR-Cas9 systems are based on the introduction of a double strand break (DSB) by the gRNA-Cas9 complex. If no exogenous DNA is provided, the DSB is repaired via NHEJ resulting in insertions and deletions (indels) of varying length. Providing an exogenous donor DNA with HAs allows marker-less HR modifications with generally increased frequencies.

(Dominguez et al., 2016) and facilitating metabolic engineering (Section 2.3).

1.2.2. Expression features and molecular parts for Cas9 and gRNA expression

CRISPR-Cas9 mediated genome editing is in principle simple, as only two components (Cas9 and gRNA) need to be co-expressed. However, there are many factors influencing Cas9/gRNA functionality (Peng et al., 2016) that may need optimization to implement efficient targeting in a certain organism (Fig. 2). Accordingly, there have been different approaches to setting up CRISPR-Cas9 systems in *S. cerevisiae* and other yeasts using various molecular parts (reviewed in the following sections).

Factors requiring optimization include nuclear localization, codon optimization and expression of Cas9 as well as gRNA expression and processing. The expression strategy and molecular parts may vary as Cas9 and/or the gRNA can be integrated into the genome or expressed from plasmid(s). Also strong/weak or constitutive/inducible promoters can be used for expression (e.g. (Jacobs et al., 2014; Weninger et al., 2016a); Fig. 2).

Both Cas9 and the gRNA need to be localized in the nucleus to cleave genomic DNA. Cas9 is typically fused to a nuclear localization sequence (NLS) to achieve nuclear targeting (Weninger et al., 2015). Nuclear targeting of gRNAs is more complex, as transcripts from RNA polymerase II (RNAP II) promoters, which are most commonly used for heterologous gene expression, are exported from the nucleus into the cytosol for translation. Transcripts from RNAP III promoters remain in

the nucleus, but these promoters are in most organisms poorly characterized. RNAP III promoters may add additional nucleotides to the gRNA that may impair its function. Therefore, self-cleaving ribozymes can be used to achieve correct processing of the gRNA (also in combination with RNAP II promoters) (Jacobs et al., 2014; Nowak et al., 2016; Weninger et al., 2016a) (Fig. 2). The strength of the promoters used for CAS9 and the gRNA expression can also have a profound influence on the targeting efficiency (Ryan and Cate, 2014; Stovicek et al., 2015b; Weninger et al., 2016a). Also the codon optimization of the CAS9 gene can influence the functionality of the CRISPR-Cas system (Weninger et al., 2016a). CAS9 and the gRNA can be integrated into the genome, provided on an episomal plasmid (Jacobs et al., 2014; Vyas et al., 2015) or even transiently expressed without genomic integration or a replicating sequence (Min et al., 2015). If both CAS9 and the gRNA are expressed episomally, they may be provided on the same or different plasmids using different replicating sequences (2 μ (Bao et al., 2015; DiCarlo et al., 2013; Generoso et al., 2016; Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b; Laughery et al., 2015; Ryan and Cate, 2014) or autonomously replicating sequences (ARSs) (Vyas et al., 2015; Weninger et al., 2016a)). In addition to all these expression features, eventually also the targeted genomic locus and the gRNA design critically influence the Cas9 efficiency (Weninger et al., 2016a). If a donor fragment is provided, the length of the homology arms and its integrity (linear or circular) affect the efficiency of its incorporation by HR (Gao et al., 2016).

Very recently a mini-review was published covering mostly genome engineering applications of CRISPR-Cas9 in yeast (Stovicek et al.,

Fig. 2. Expression features and molecular parts for Cas9 and gRNA expression to implement efficient CRISPR-Cas9 mediated genome editing.

The gRNA and Cas9 need to be functionally co-expressed to introduce a targeted double strand break (DSB) in the genome. The two modules can be expressed either from the same plasmid, separate plasmids or integrated into the genome. Transient expression of gRNAs from PCR products (DiCarlo et al., 2013) and CAS9 + gRNA from linear plasmids without replication sequences (Min et al., 2015) have also been demonstrated. RNA polymerase (RNAP) II or III promoters can be used to express the gRNA and CAS9. While RNAP II transcripts are exported and translated in the cytosol (as desired for CAS9 expression), RNAP III transcripts remain in the nucleus (as desired for gRNAs). gRNAs may contain additional 5' and 3' sequences added in the transcription process that can be removed using ribozymes (e.g. hammerhead, HH or hepatitis delta virus, HDV) or synthetic RNAP III promoters (Schwartz et al., 2016). Also different gRNA designs are shown: Naturally a CRISPR targeting RNA (crRNA) and a *trans*-activating crRNA (tracrRNA) bind to each other. In most genome editing applications, the crRNA and tracrRNA are fused, resulting in a single guide RNA (sgRNA) (Jinek et al., 2012). The sgRNA consists of a structural part and a variable 20 bp part that is adapted to match the genomic target sequence (Jinek et al., 2012; Mali et al., 2013). For some multiplexing strategies, nonetheless, crRNA/tracrRNA hybrids are used (Bao et al., 2015). Similarly, Cas9 functionality is influenced by the expression strategy (promoter, codon optimization) and nuclear localization sequence (NLS) used. For both gRNA and CAS9 cassettes transcriptional terminators (TTs) are needed. Optional donor fragments can be provided to promote HR (Fig. 1). Donor incorporation is influenced by the length of the homology arms (HAs), linear/circular form and presence of a marker. Elements of this figure are based on Figs. 1 and 2 from (Weninger et al., 2016a).

2017). We herein offer a comprehensive review of the implementation of efficient CRISPR-Cas9 vector designs, compare critical factors in different yeast species and discuss various advanced CRISPR-related applications including metabolic engineering endeavours. Appendix A - Supplementary data provides also a concrete example highlighting key design steps to achieve gene deletion in yeast. As the community working with *S. cerevisiae* is much larger than for other yeasts, considerably more vector systems and applications have been reported to date. Therefore, state of the art CRISPR-Cas9 systems and advanced applications in *S. cerevisiae* are reviewed here first. Subsequently CRISPR-Cas9 systems beyond *S. cerevisiae* are discussed and difficulties and possible improvements highlighted.

2. Tools and applications in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

In *S. cerevisiae*, several CRISPR-Cas9 implementations have been established relying on different molecular parts, expression features and cloning methods for the gRNA (Section 2.1, Table 1). Various genome editing (Section 2.2, Table 2) and advanced applications, such as regulating transcription (Section 2.3.1, Table 3) have been reported. CRISPR-Cas9 has also been successfully applied to facilitate heterologous pathway expression and to enable novel metabolic engineering approaches in *S. cerevisiae* (Sections 2.3.2–2.3.4, Table 3).

2.1. CRISPR-Cas9 expression strategies

The application of CRISPR-Cas9 for genome editing of *S. cerevisiae* was first described by the group of George M. Church (DiCarlo et al., 2013). The endonuclease Cas9 (fused to a SV40 nuclear localization signal at its C-terminus) was expressed from a centromeric plasmid and a sgRNA was expressed either from a PCR cassette, or from a 2μ plasmid. Two different promoters for CAS9 expression (inducible and constitutive) and templates for homology recombination (single- or double-stranded oligonucleotides) were tested (Table 1). Nearly 100% recombination frequency was achieved in cells constitutively expressing CAS9 (*TEF1* promoter) that were co-transformed with the gRNA 2μ plasmid and a double-stranded 90-mer homology fragment. This donor fragment was designed to disrupt the original PAM sequence. Generally, either the gRNA target site or the PAM sequence has to be altered

by the donor repair fragment in order to protect the targeted genome site from repeated Cas9 cleavage. The high targeting efficiency was reached even though no selection marker was integrated into the genome.

After CRISPR-Cas was once established in *S. cerevisiae*, an increasing number of variations of the original system (DiCarlo et al., 2013) and strategies to facilitate the molecular cloning of new gRNAs into vectors were developed (Table 1). The variations of the original set-up generally include different promoters for the expression of CAS9 and gRNA, codon optimized-sequences and mutations of CAS9, gRNA design (*i.e.* sgRNA or crRNA + tracrRNA), and strategies for CRISPR-Cas9 expression (plasmid vs. genomic integration, one plasmid vs. two plasmids).

2.1.1. Variations of CAS9 and gRNA expression

The constitutive *TEF1* promoter was mostly used for the expression of CAS9 in *S. cerevisiae* (Table 1), with no negative effect on the specific growth rate of the strains (Mans et al., 2015; Sasano et al., 2016). However, a negative effect of CAS9 expression from the *TEF1* promoter was shown in the absence of gRNA as a low number of transformants was obtained (Ronda et al., 2015). A more detailed study on the toxic effects of a high Cas9 load on the cell would be interesting, since to date little is known about its mechanism. Several additional promoters for CAS9 expression were tested (Table 1). In detail, expression of CAS9 from strong promoters (*HXT7*, *TDH3*) was reported to negatively influence the growth and fitness of the strains (Generoso et al., 2016; Ryan and Cate, 2014). Using the copper-inducible *CUP1* promoter, a decreased targeting efficiency (< 20%) was noticed, possibly caused by time-limited expression of CAS9 (Ronda et al., 2015). In another study, constitutive and low expression of CAS9 from the weak *ADH1* promoter was shown to have beneficial effects on the editing efficiency (Stovicek et al., 2015b). Other weak (*ROX3*) (Generoso et al., 2016) or medium-strength (*FBA1*, *RNR2*) (Horwitz et al., 2015; Ryan and Cate, 2014) promoters were also found to be sufficient for CAS9 expression (Horwitz et al., 2015) or to have no negative impact on the strain's growth rate (Generoso et al., 2016; Ryan and Cate, 2014), suggesting that rather low expression levels of CAS9 are favourable.

In addition to the different promoters used for CAS9 expression, also differently codon optimized CAS9 sequences have been tested. The natural sequence from *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Homo sapiens*-codon

Table 1
Design and molecular parts of CRISPR-Cas9 vectors in *S. cerevisiae*.

Cassette for CAS9 ^a /gRNA expression (regulation of promoter)	Strategy	gRNA cloning method	Reference
<i>P_{Gal-L}</i> ^b or <i>P_{TEF1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong inducible or strong constitutive) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Episomal (CEN) plasmid bearing CAS9 expression cassette; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette/PCR cassette for transient gRNA expression, and donor fragment	Gibson assembly	DiCarlo et al. (2013)
<i>P_{TPGI}</i> ^c – ScdCAS9 ^d -VP64 ^e – <i>CYC1TT</i> (synthetic inducible) <i>P_{RPR1}</i> – gRNA – <i>RPR1TT</i> (constitutive)	Integration of the dCAS9 expression vector in the genome; Transformation of the dCAS9 expression strain with episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette	Gibson assembly	Farzadfard et al. (2013)
<i>P_{TDH3}</i> – HsdCAS9 ^d – (<i>Mxi1</i>) (strong) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Co-transformations of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with the episomal (CEN/ARS) plasmid bearing dCAS9 expression cassette and the episomal (CEN) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette	Standard ligation/insertion protocols	Gilbert et al. (2013)
<i>P_{TDH3}</i> – dCAS9 ^d – <i>CYC1TT</i> or <i>P_{TEF1}</i> – dCAS9 ^d – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA(2xPP7 ^f) – <i>SUP4TT</i> or <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA(2xMS2(wt + f6)) – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Co-transformation of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with plasmid bearing CAS9 expression cassette and episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing single or multiple gRNA expression cassette(s)	USER cloning	Jensen et al. (2017)
<i>P_{RNR2}</i> – SpCAS9 – 8xHIS – <i>CYC1TT</i> (moderately strong) <i>P_{IRNA,Phc}</i> -HDV-gRNA	Co-transformations of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with the single episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing CAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes, and <i>in vivo</i> assembling donor fragments	Ligation independent cloning (LIC)	Ryan and Cate (2014)
<i>P_{TEF1}</i> – FLAG – SpiCAS9 ^g – <i>ADH2TT</i> <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – crRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i> <i>P_{RPR1}</i> – tracrRNA – <i>RPR1TT</i>	Single episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing iCAS9 and gRNA ^h expression cassettes and donor fragments	Golden Gate assembly	Bao et al. (2015), Shi et al. (2016)
<i>P_{FBA1}</i> – ScCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (moderately strong) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Integration of linear CAS9 expression construct in the genome; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with an <i>in vivo</i> assembling plasmid backbone bearing a selection marker, PCR cassettes bearing gRNAs, and donor fragments	<i>in vivo</i> homologous recombination	Horwitz et al. (2015)
<i>P_{TEF1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Episomal (CEN) plasmid bearing CAS9 expression cassette; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette, and (<i>in vivo</i> assembling) donor fragments	USER cloning	Jakociunas et al. (2015a, 2015b)
<i>P_{TDH3}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>ADH1TT</i> <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Co-transformations of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with the single episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing CAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes, and donor fragments	Hybridization (T4 DNA ligase buffer) and ligation (Z-competent <i>E. coli</i> , Zymo Research)	Laughery et al. (2015)
<i>P_{TEF1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Integration of CAS9 expression PCR cassette in the genome; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with <i>in vivo</i> assembling episomal (2μ) plasmid backbone bearing a selection marker, PCR cassettes bearing gRNAs, and donor fragments	Gibson assembly, <i>in vivo</i> homologous recombination	Mans et al. (2015)
<i>P_{TEF1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> or <i>P_{CUP1}</i> – SpCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (constitutive or inducible) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Integration of CAS9 expression vector in the genome; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with integrative vector bearing gRNA expression cassette, and donor fragments or Episomal (CEN/ARS) plasmid bearing CAS9 expression cassette; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette, and EasyClone donor fragments	USER cloning	Ronda et al. (2015)
<i>P_{TEF1/PADH1}</i> – yeastCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong/weak) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Episomal (CEN/ARS) plasmid bearing CAS9 expression cassette; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing gRNA expression cassette, and donor fragments	USER cloning	Stovicek et al. (2015b)
<i>P_{PROX3/P_{RNR2}/P_{TDH2}/P_{HXT7}}</i> – ScCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (weak/moderate/strong/strong) <i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>	Co-transformations of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with (<i>in vivo</i> assembling) single episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing CAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes, and donor fragments	<i>in vivo</i> homologous recombination or Gibson assembly	Generoso et al. (2016)
<i>P_{TPGI}</i> ^c – ScdCAS9 ^d -VP64 ^e – IAA degenon – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{ADH1}</i> – HH – gRNA – HDV	Episomal (CEN) plasmid bearing dCAS9 expression cassette; integration of gRNA expression construct in the genome	Not specified	(Khakhar et al., 2016)
<i>P_{TEF1}</i> – HsdCAS9 ^d – (<i>Mxi1</i>) – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{RPR1}</i> – <i>NotI</i> site – gRNA (inducible)	Single episomal (CEN/ARS) plasmid bearing dCAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes	Gibson assembly	Smith et al. (2016)
<i>P_{ADH1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{IRNA,Tyr}</i> – gRNA – (HDV –) SNR52TT	Co-transformations of <i>S. cerevisiae</i> strain with (<i>in vivo</i> assembling) single episomal (2μ) plasmid bearing CAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes, and donor DNA	Gibson assembly or <i>in vivo</i> homologous recombination	Reider Apel et al. (2017)

^a Codon usage of CAS9: Hs – human codon optimized CAS9, Sc – *S. cerevisiae* codon optimized CAS9, Sp – *S. pyogenes* CAS9 (native codon usage).

^b An attenuated version of the strongly galactose-inducible *GAL1* promoter.

^c Synthetic galactose + anhydrotetracycline inducible promoter (Ellis et al., 2009).

^d Endonuclease-deficient Cas9.

^e Four repeats of the minimal domain of the herpes simplex viral protein 16 (VP16).

^f RNA scaffolds.

^g Improved Cas9.

^h Shi et al. (2016) adapted the system by Bao et al. (2015) and replaced the crRNA and tracrRNA with delta site-specific gRNA.

Table 2
Genome editing applications of CRISPR-Cas9 in haploid and polyploid *S. cerevisiae* strains.

Genetic modification	Targeting efficiency ^a		Reference
	CAS9 + gRNA	CAS9 + gRNA + donor	
Haploid strains			
Single			
CAN1 disruption (1 gRNA)	0 %	99%	DiCarlo et al. (2013)
CAN1 disruption (1 gRNA)	n.d.	5.82–100%	Bao et al. (2015)
ADE2 disruption (1 gRNA)	Not specified	12.5–100%	Stovicek et al. (2015b)
Disruption of ADE2 with dsDNA oligo (1 gRNA)	16%	95%	Mans et al. (2015)
Deletion of MCH1 (1 gRNA)	Not specified	50% (in vivo assembly)	Laughery et al. (2015)
Deletion of MCH2 (1 gRNA)	Not specified	25% (in vivo assembly)	Horwitz et al. (2015)
Deletion of MCH5 (1 gRNA)	Not specified	75% (in vivo assembly)	Biot-Pelletier and Martin (2016)
Point mutations in TRP1 (single nucleotide deletion, two nucleotide substitutions) (1 gRNA)	56% or 83% <i>trp⁻</i> (with low-copy or high-copy CAS9 expression vector, resp.) (NHLEJ)	96–100%	Nishida et al. (2016)
Single point mutation in different alleles (ACE2, SEC1, SEC6, MYO2, CDC28, NCS2, END3, SPT15, PRO1) (1 gRNA)	Not specified	9–100%	Horowitz et al. (2015)
Point mutation in promoter of GSH1 gene (1 gRNA per step, two steps)	Not specified	Not specified	Horowitz et al. (2015)
Point mutation in CAN1 gene (1 gRNA)	94.7% by dCas9 D10A-PmCDA1, 96.1% by nCas9 D10A-PmCDA1	- (donor-free method)	Horowitz et al. (2015)
Point mutation in ADE1 gene (1 gRNA)	16–47% by nCas9 D10A-PmCDA1 depending on the target site (efficiency considered according to the number of phenotypic mutants)	- (donor-free method)	Horowitz et al. (2015)
Deletion of ILV1 (1 gRNA)	Not specified	~100% (pre-assembled plasmid), ~60% (in vivo assembling plasmid)	Generoso et al. (2016)
Single split of chromosome XV (using 400 bp homology sequences) (1 gRNA)	Not specified	100%	Sasano et al. (2016)
Single split of chromosome XVI (using 400 bp homology sequences) (1 gRNA)	Not specified	100%	Stovicek et al. (2015b)
Simultaneous disruption of ADE2 and knock-in of GFP (1 gRNA)	Not specified	97%	Generoso et al. (2016)
Simultaneous deletion of LEU4 and LEU9 (1 gRNA)	Not specified	~95% (pre-assembled plasmid), ~10% (in vivo assembling plasmid)	Mans et al. (2015)
Simultaneous deletion of ITR1 and PDR12 (2 gRNAs)	Low number of colonies	100%	Mans et al. (2015)
Combined deletions (ACS1 and ACS2) with integration of <i>E. faecalis</i> pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (<i>pdhA</i> , <i>pdhB</i> , <i>aceF</i> , <i>lplA</i> and <i>lplA2</i>) (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	100%	Stovicek et al. (2015b)
Simultaneous single-nucleotide mutations in <i>GET4</i> and <i>NATI1</i> (2 gRNAs)	No colonies	25%	Generoso et al. (2016)
Point mutation in alleles <i>NCS2</i> and <i>END3</i> (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	9%	Horwitz et al. (2015)
Simultaneous deletion of <i>ILV1</i> , <i>LEU4</i> and <i>LEU9</i> (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	~95% (pre-assembled plasmid), 0% (in vivo assembling plasmid – no transformants)	Generoso et al. (2016)
Deletion of large chromosomal region (38 kbp) (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	10%	Hao et al. (2016)
Simultaneous double split of chromosomes XV and XVI (using 400 bp homology sequences) (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	50%	Sasano et al. (2016)
Simultaneous double split of the same chromosome XII (using 400 bp homology sequences) (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	40%	Bao et al. (2015)
Simultaneous double split of the same chromosome XII/IV (using 50 bp homology sequences) (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	20%/10%	Bao et al. (2015)
Simultaneous disruption of <i>CAN1</i> , <i>LYP1</i> , <i>ADE2</i> (3 gRNAs)	Not specified	27–87%	Nishida et al. (2016)
Simultaneous disruption of genes involved in hydrocortisone biosynthetic pathway (<i>AIT2</i> , <i>GCY1</i> , <i>YPR1</i>) (3 gRNAs)	Not specified	100%	Mans et al. (2015)
Simultaneous introduction of point mutations into <i>ADE1</i> and <i>CAN1</i> (2 gRNAs)	31% by nCas9 D10A-PmCDA1 (efficiency considered according to the number of phenotypic mutants)	- (donor-free method)	Nishida et al. (2016)
Simultaneous deletion of <i>MCH1</i> , <i>MCH2</i> and <i>MCH5</i> (3 gRNAs)	Not specified	0% (in vivo assembly)	Mans et al. (2015)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Genetic modification	Details	Targeting efficiency ^a		Reference	
		CAS9 + gRNA	CAS9 + gRNA + donor		
Not specified	Simultaneous triple split of chromosomes IV, XV and XVI, or XII, XV and XVI (using 50 bp homology sequences) (3 gRNAs)	Not specified	40%/16%	Sasano et al. (2016)	
	Simultaneous triple split of the same chromosome IV (using 50 bp homology sequences) (3 gRNAs)	Not specified	20%	Mans et al. (2015)	
	Simultaneous deletion of <i>ITRI</i> , <i>PDR12</i> , <i>MCHI</i> and <i>MCH2</i> (4 gRNAs)	Not specified	70%	Horwitz et al. (2015)	
	Simultaneous point mutations (three in <i>SPT15</i> , one in <i>PRO1 D154N</i>) and the deletion of <i>PUT1</i> (4 gRNAs)	Not specified	27%	Sasano et al. (2016)	
	Simultaneous quadruple split of chromosomes IV, XII, XV and XVI (using 50 bp homology sequences) (4 gRNAs)	Not specified	20%	Mans et al. (2015)	
	Simultaneous deletion of <i>ITRI</i> , <i>PDR12</i> , <i>MCHI</i> , <i>MCH2</i> , <i>MCH5</i> and <i>AQY1</i> (6 gRNAs)	Not specified	65%	Laugherly et al. (2015)	
	Point mutations or deletions in promoters (<i>RAD2, RFX1</i>) or gene-coding regions (<i>ESA1</i> , <i>RAD4</i> , <i>RNR1</i> , <i>STH1</i>)	Not specified	Not specified	Laugherly et al. (2015)	
	Insertion of PCR constructs bearing <i>lacZ</i> or <i>HIS3</i> gene and C-terminal tags	Not specified	Not specified		
	Diploid/polyploid strains				
	Single	Integration of nourseothricin-resistance (<i>Nat⁸</i>) cassette in diploid strain (1 gRNA)	Not specified	85%	Ryan and Cate (2014)
	Integration of nourseothricin-resistance (<i>Nat⁸</i>) cassette in polyploid strain (1 gRNA)	Not specified	68%		
	Sequential deletion of <i>URA3</i> , <i>TRP1</i> , <i>LEU2</i> and <i>HIS3</i> (1 gRNA per step)	Not specified	15–60%	Zhang et al. (2014)	
	Disruption of <i>ADE2</i> with dsDNA oligo (1 gRNA)	3%	65–78%	Stovicek et al. (2015b)	
	Simultaneous disruption of <i>ADE2</i> and knock-in of <i>GFP</i> (1 gRNA)	Not specified	81–92%	Generoso et al. (2016)	
	Deletion of <i>ILV1</i> (1 gRNA)	Not specified	~98% (pre-assembled plasmid), ~60% (<i>in vivo</i> assembling plasmid)	Generoso et al. (2016)	
	Simultaneous deletion of <i>LEU4</i> and <i>LEU9</i> (1 gRNA)	Not specified	~98% (pre-assembled plasmid), ~30% (<i>in vivo</i> assembling plasmid)	Generoso et al. (2016)	
	Simultaneous deletion of <i>ILV1</i> and <i>LEU4/9</i> loci (2 gRNAs)	Not specified	0% for both pre-assembled plasmid as well as <i>in vivo</i> assembling plasmid (no transformants)		
	Simultaneous introduction of point mutations into <i>ADE1</i> and <i>CAN1</i> (2 gRNAs)	14% by nCas9 D10A-PmCDA1 (efficiency considered according to the number of phenotypic mutants)	- (donor-free method)	Nishida et al. (2016)	

^a In *S. cerevisiae*, HR is preferred over NHEJ for repairing DSBs (Agmon et al., 2009; Bao et al., 2015) and the vast majority of publications on CRISPR-Cas in *S. cerevisiae* have focused on HR via donor fragments with homology arms. However, in other yeasts, NHEJ may be prevalent and lead to NHEJ mediated repair even if a donor fragment is provided (Table 5).

Table 3
Toolbox of advanced CRISPR related applications in *S. cerevisiae*.

Application	Intervention	Efficiency	Reference
Regulation of transcription	Regulation of <i>TEF1</i> promoter expressing GFP by crisprTF with Mxi1 repressor	53-fold decrease in activity	Gilbert et al. (2013)
	Regulation of <i>CYC1</i> promoter expressing GFP by crisprTF with VP64 activator	Approx. 7-fold decrease to 3-fold increase in activity, depending on gRNA binding position and their combinations	Farzadfard et al. (2013)
	Regulation of synthetic <i>CYC1</i> promoter expressing EBFP with 12 gRNA sites by crisprTF with VP64 activator	Up to 70-fold increase in activity	
	Regulation of <i>CYC1</i> promoter expressing EGFP by auxin-degradable crisprTF with VP64	Approx. 7-fold increase in activity in absence of auxin, no effect in presence of auxin	Khakhar et al. (2016)
	Regulation of <i>ERG11</i> , <i>ERG25</i> , <i>CRG1</i> , <i>SEC14</i> genes by crisprTF with Mxi1 repressor	Up to 10-fold decrease of transcript	Smith et al. (2016)
	Regulation of <i>HMG1</i> promoter by Mxi1 repressor or VPR (VP64-p65-Rta) activator	1.5-fold decrease by dCas9-Mxi1, 1.2-fold decrease by scRNA mediating Mxi1, 1.6-fold increase in activity by dCas9-VPR, 1.3-fold increase in activity by scRNA mediating VPR	Jensen et al. (2017)
	Regulation of <i>OLE1</i> promoter by Mxi1 repressor or VPR (VP64-p65-Rta) activator	2.6-fold decrease by dCas9-Mxi1, 1.3-fold decrease by scRNA mediating Mxi1, no significant increase in activity by dCas9-VPR, no increase in activity by scRNA mediating VPR	
	Regulation of mevalonate pathway promoters (<i>ERG8</i> , <i>ERG9</i> , <i>ERG12</i> , <i>ERG19</i> , <i>ERG20</i> , <i>HMG1</i> , <i>HMG2</i> , <i>BTS2</i>) or glycolytic promoters (<i>TDH3</i> , <i>TEF1</i> , <i>PGK1</i> , <i>RNR2</i>) by Mxi1 repressor or VPR (VP64-p65-Rta) activator mediated by scRNA	Up to 3-fold decrease in activity, up to 2.3-fold increase in activity	
	Regulation of promoters of triacylglycerol (TAG) biosynthetic pathway (<i>OLE1</i> , <i>DGAI1</i>) by dCas9-VPR	Increase of TAG levels 1.5-fold when expressing single gRNAs, > 2-fold when co-expressing the two gRNAs	
	Regulation of carotenoid production by simultaneous (scRNAs) repression of promoters <i>ERG20</i> and <i>TDH3</i> , and activation of promoter <i>ERG9</i>	1.4-fold decrease of β -carotene production	
Metabolic engineering	Regulation of naringenin production pathway by repression of <i>TSC13</i> transcription	Approx. 1.65-fold increase of naringenin production	Vanegas et al. (2017)
	Integration of 24 kbp butanediol synthetic pathway and xylose utilization pathway	Approx. 57%	Shi et al. (2016)
	Integration of 24 kbp muconic acid biosynthetic pathway	4.2%, function defect in one enzyme involved in the pathway	Horwitz et al. (2015)
	Integration of carotenoid production pathway	84%	Ronda et al. (2015)
	Integration of carotenoid production pathway	30.6%	Jakociunas et al. (2015a)
	Engineering of tyrosine biosynthetic pathway (knock-out of two genes)	58%	
	Integration of <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> pyruvate dehydrogenase complex	60–70% for haploid strain, not specified for diploid strain	Jessop-Fabre et al. (2016)
	Engineering of mevalonate biosynthetic pathway (deletion of 3 genes, knock-out of 1 gene, down-regulation of one gene)	100% (4 clones tested)	Jakociunas et al. (2015b)
	Engineering of lactic acid production pathway (disruption of two genes)	70% for haploid strain, 36% for diploid strain	Stovicek et al. (2015b)
	Reduction of ethyl carbamate production (knock-out of <i>CAR1</i> gene)	89% (deletion)	Chin et al. (2016)
Optimization of gene expression Manipulation of natural or synthetic genomes in <i>S. cerevisiae</i>	Integration of naringenin production pathway (five genes)	100% (nonsense mutation) (2 clones tested)	Vanegas et al. (2017)
	Two-step multiple integration of xylose assimilation pathway cassette (three genes) with simultaneous deletion of endogenous genes <i>PHO13</i> and <i>ALD6</i> ; step 1 – integration of xylose assimilation pathway cassette into <i>PHO13</i> locus, step 2 – integration of a second xylose assimilation pathway cassette into <i>ALD6</i> locus	100% Step 1 – 17–25% depending on the length of the overlapping sequence in the donor cassette, step 2 – 50%	Tsai et al. (2015)
	Improvement of taxadiene production	25-fold increase in titer	Reider Apel et al. (2017)
	Simultaneous insertion of four promoter cassettes into a silent biosynthetic gene cluster	26% (lazarimide cluster) 51% (aromatic polyketide cluster AB1210) 80% and 50% for first and second round, respectively of two-round insertion (tetarimycin cluster)	Kang et al. (2016)
	Deletion of <i>glpO</i> (glycerol-3-phosphate oxidase) gene from <i>Mycoplasma mycoides</i> subsp. <i>capri</i> GM12 (Mmc) genome	20%	Tsarmopoulos et al. (2016)

optimized or *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*-codon optimized sequences have been used for genome editing in *S. cerevisiae* (Table 1). An improved *S. pyogenes* Cas9 protein (iCas9) was obtained inadvertently during a plasmid construction, by introducing two accidental point mutations into the original *S. pyogenes* CAS9, in a region that is critical for the DNA cleavage of the Cas9 protein. This mutant variant had higher gene disruption efficiency than the wild type Cas9 while no increase in off-target effects were observed (Bao et al., 2015). The nickase Cas9

variants nCas9 D10A and nCas9 H840A were shown to be comparably effective in stimulating HR in *S. cerevisiae*, but both with lower rates than the DSB-inducing Cas9 (Satomura et al., 2017).

An SV40 nuclear localization sequence (NLS) is typically fused to the Cas9, to ensure its import to the nucleus. Most typically, a single NLS is fused to either an N- or a C-terminus of the Cas9 (DiCarlo et al., 2013; Farzadfard et al., 2013; Generoso et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b; Khakhar et al., 2016; Laughery

Fig. 3. Single plasmid HI-CRISPR-Cas (homology-integrated) system designed for facilitated multiplexing in *S. cerevisiae* by (Bao et al., 2015). Donor fragments and the variable parts (20 bps) of the gRNAs are cloned together in an array separated by direct repeats. A tracrRNA/crRNA system is used, where the gRNA consists of two RNAs. The crRNAs containing the variable parts of the guide RNAs are transcribed together with the donor fragments into a pre-crRNA. The pre-crRNA is processed into mature crRNA(s) by RNase III and unknown cellular nuclease(s). iCas9 and the tracrRNA are expressed from separate modules. The three components, iCas9, mature crRNA and tracrRNA are then complexed to form the functional CRISPR-Cas system. Depending on the crRNA incorporated, different positions in the genome are cleaved and the donor fragments from the plasmid inserted by HR. * Note that the donor is also transcribed as part of the crRNA. It is not clear if the transcribed HR donor is fully cleaved from the crRNA.

et al., 2015; Mans et al., 2015; Reider Apel et al., 2017; Ronda et al., 2015; Ryan and Cate, 2014; Smith et al., 2016; Stovicek et al., 2015b), but also a double C- and N-terminus fusion (Bao et al., 2015), or two C-terminal NLSs were used (Gilbert et al., 2013). In the same way, also gRNA expression has been varied by using different promoters and alternative gRNA designs (sgRNA vs. paired crRNA/tracrRNA combinations, Fig. 2). The *SNR52* promoter is predominantly used for the expression of gRNAs (Table 1), but in case of editing polyploid *S. cerevisiae* strains, the use of a tRNA promoter was reported to be beneficial (Ryan and Cate, 2014). While the *SNR52* promoter led to very low homozygosity efficiency of 5%, the tRNA^{Ph} promoter yielded nearly 100% efficiency of homozygosity. gRNAs have also been functionally expressed from inducible promoters to activate/repress transcription using crisprTFs (see Chapter 2.3.1) (Jensen et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016).

In the majority of applications, a chimeric single-guide RNA (Jinek et al., 2012) was used to target the endonuclease Cas9 to a specific DNA sequence. However, within a Homology-Integrated CRISPR-Cas9 (HI-CRISPR) system (Bao et al., 2015), the gRNA consisted of a CRISPR targeting RNA (crRNA) and *trans*-activating crRNA (tracrRNA), which is identical to the natural occurrence in the bacterial type II CRISPR-Cas system (Deltcheva et al., 2011; Jinek et al., 2012). The HI-CRISPR system takes advantage of the natural polycistronic character of CRISPR; a cassette driven by a single promoter consisted of multiple spacers flanked by direct repeats (Fig. 3). Each spacer was used in *S. cerevisiae* as a source of donor fragment and crRNA at the same time, assuming that the crRNA is cleaved from the transcribed spacer (i.e. pre-crRNA) by host RNase III and unknown nuclease(s). Using this “polycistronic” strategy, it was possible to achieve a triple disruption in *S. cerevisiae* with up to 87% efficiency. However, at maximum four consecutive crRNAs could have been used for functional multiplexing, possibly because of an incomplete transcription and/or instability of the long crRNA. While this system considerably simplifies the preparation and cloning of donors and gRNAs in *S. cerevisiae*, it is unclear if this strategy would also work in other yeasts. As discussed in Sections 1.2.1 and 3, other yeasts often need considerably longer homology arms in donor fragments than *S. cerevisiae*. In addition, the donor DNA fragment is transcribed together with the crRNAs. Hence the crRNA contains an

additional 5' overhang that may impair its function in non-conventional yeasts, where exact processing of the gRNA was found to be crucial (Section 3).

While the original CRISPR-Cas9 set-up for *S. cerevisiae* (DiCarlo et al., 2013) provided the Cas9 and gRNA on two different vectors, some researchers expressed both components from a single plasmid (Bao et al., 2015; Generoso et al., 2016; Laughery et al., 2015; Reider Apel et al., 2017; Ryan and Cate, 2014; Smith et al., 2016). The advantage of the single plasmid system is that it requires only one selection marker and does not have to be co-transformed with another vector. On the other hand, the delivery of Cas9 and gRNA on two separate vectors is a safety precaution preventing the CRISPR-Cas system to accidentally alter wild populations in case of leakage of the genetic material beyond the laboratory, as gRNA alone cannot bias inheritance in the absence of Cas9 and *vice versa* (DiCarlo et al., 2015).

2.1.2. Enhanced cloning of gRNAs

Once a plasmid for efficient CRISPR-Cas9 mediated genome editing has been implemented, the gRNA needs to be exchanged for every new gene that should be targeted. This exchange typically requires PCR amplifications, assembly methods, uracil-specific excision reaction (USER) and/or synthesis of large gene blocks (Bao et al., 2015; DiCarlo et al., 2013; Jakociunas et al., 2015b; Ryan and Cate, 2014; Zhang et al., 2014). Certain approaches were proposed to make the cloning step more simple, rapid and inexpensive, or even to make it obsolete. These include a design of a sgRNA expression cassette with unique restriction enzyme sites (Laughery et al., 2015) or a cloning-free *in vivo* assembly approach (Generoso et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Jakociunas et al., 2015a; Mans et al., 2015; Reider Apel et al., 2017).

A simplification as well as cost reduction of the cloning procedure was achieved by designing an sgRNA expression cassette with unique *BclI* and *SwaI* restriction enzyme sites (Laughery et al., 2015). This approach enables insertion of any 20 bp gRNA sequence that includes overhangs complementary to the *SwaI*- and *BclI*- pre-digested RNA cassette. (Mans et al., 2015) suggested a smart exchange of the gRNA sequence within a gRNA-carrying cassette. This can be done *in vivo* by homologous recombination of the desired gRNA fragment with the vector backbone, within a single co-transformation step also including a repair HR-oligonucleotide. The gRNA was successfully exchanged in up to 75% of the tested transformants. A successful *in vivo* assembly of a linear backbone containing CAS9, and a single PCR-generated cassette carrying gRNA was also demonstrated (Generoso et al., 2016; Reider Apel et al., 2017). However, the efficiency of the *in vivo* approach was lower (~10–60%, 85% respectively), in comparison to transformation with a pre-assembled Cas9-gRNA plasmid (90–100%, 100% respectively). The *in vivo* assembly of a plasmid containing multiple gRNA fragments (and corresponding repair fragments) led to very low efficiency of only 4%, likely caused by an incorrect annealing of the fragments within the *in vivo* recombination (Mans et al., 2015), or no colonies after the transformation at all (Generoso et al., 2016).

In contrast, a high rate of triple integration (64%) was reported by (Horwitz et al., 2015), using a method termed ‘CAM’ (CRISPR-Cas-Assisted Multiplexing) (Walter et al., 2016). Three linear PCR cassettes carrying the gRNAs, and a single linearized vector backbone were supplied within the transformation step. Cas9 was expressed in the cells prior to the transformation with the other components (Horwitz et al., 2015; Mans et al., 2015). Furthermore, a method named CasEMBLR (Cas9-facilitated multiloci integration of assembled DNA parts into *S. cerevisiae* chromosomes) was based on an *in vivo* assembly approach (Jakociunas et al., 2015a). The genes to be integrated into *S. cerevisiae* chromosomes were supplied in a form of fragmented expression cassettes consisting of five overlapping fragments (fragments homologous to the region of the double strand break caused by Cas9, promoter, structural gene and terminator). Cells expressing CAS9 were co-transformed with the five-part integration cassettes and a single plasmid carrying the multiple gRNAs. When targeting an individual locus, the

efficiency of *in vivo* assembly and integration of the cassette was 77–96% (14.6% when choosing an unsuitable target site within the locus). The efficiency of a simultaneous *in vivo* assembly and integration of three cassettes was 30.6%.

CRISPR-Cas9 was employed along with an EasyClone genome editing tool (Jensen et al., 2014; Stovicek et al., 2015a) to increase the efficiency and accuracy of multiple integrations in a single-step (Jessop-Fabre et al., 2016; Ronda et al., 2015). The EasyClone integration plasmids enable fast and simultaneous multiple integrations of genes of interest into well-characterized genomic integration sites. Each integration cassette can carry one or two genes (using one-directional or bi-directional promoter, respectively).

2.1.3. Approaches to increase targeting efficiency and reduce off-targeting

In addition to testing different promoters and plasmid/integration systems (Table 1, Table 2), a few more factors were reported to increase the efficiency of introducing targeted mutations. These factors include a high copy number of the CRISPR-Cas9 system (Bao et al., 2015) or an increased abundance of gRNA. An increased abundance of gRNA can be reached by expressing the gRNA from a strong RNAP II promoter and by fusing the gRNA to self-cleaving ribozymes (e.g. hepatitis delta virus (HDV) ribozyme). Thereby the gRNA transcript level is increased and processing as well as stability are improved by protecting the gRNA from exonucleases (Jacobs et al., 2014; Ryan and Cate, 2014). However, (Reider Apel et al., 2017) reported a negative impact of HDV ribozyme fusion on the performance of a certain gRNA as the modification efficiency improved 2.5-fold when the ribozyme was removed.

Another important factor is the choice of the gRNA binding site, as there appear to be easily- as well as poorly-targetable sites in close proximity (Bao et al., 2015; Jakociunas et al., 2015a). The poor targeting efficiency may be associated with chromatin inaccessibility (e.g. telomere regions) or high nucleosome occupancy (Reider Apel et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016), or also with a secondary structure of the 20 nt gRNA (Jakociunas et al., 2015a). In contrast, (Smith et al., 2016) predicted no strong effect of the gRNA secondary structure on its guiding efficiency. Truncated gRNAs (17 or 18 nt) have been reported to reduce off-targeting in other organisms (Fu et al., 2014; Osakabe et al., 2016). However, in *S. cerevisiae* truncated gRNAs did not exhibit a considerable improvement in efficiency nor in specificity compared to a full-length version (20 nt), suggesting that truncated gRNAs do not reduce off-targeting in *S. cerevisiae* (Smith et al., 2016).

In addition to these gRNA/plasmid related issues, also the length of homology arms of the donor DNA may also be crucial to the targeting efficiency (Bao et al., 2015; Ronda et al., 2015). Within the lengths of homology arms tested (10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 bp), the disruption efficiency of *CAN1* was the highest when using 50 bp homology arms flanking the Cas9 cutting site (Bao et al., 2015). In another work, the length of homology arms of an integration donor DNA was 60, 110 or 500 bp. In case of a single integration, the efficiency was nearly 100%, independently of the length. However, a triple simultaneous integration only worked well with the 500 bp homology arms (Ronda et al., 2015).

Also modified transformation protocols helped to increase targeting efficiencies. A prolonged incubation of cells in a liquid medium after transformation was reported to increase the efficiency; however, this strategy is not applicable for disruptions that yield mutants with growth defective phenotype (Bao et al., 2015).

Very recently also the use of an alternative RNA guided DNA endonuclease to Cas9, Cpf1 has been reported in *S. cerevisiae* (Swiat et al., 2017; Verwaal et al., 2017) allowing the recognition of different PAM sequences and thereby expanding the CRISPR toolkit.

2.2. Genome editing applications of CRISPR-Cas9 in *S. cerevisiae*

Due to the possibility of precise and simple targeting of almost any sequence within a genome by a 20 nucleotide gRNA, and very high efficiency of homologous recombination stimulated by Cas9-induced

DNA breaks, the manipulation of the *S. cerevisiae* genome has been considerably facilitated. As discussed in the following sections, the CRISPR-Cas9 technique has enabled highly efficient, seamless and marker-less genome manipulations of multiple target sites in a single step in *S. cerevisiae*. These changes included deletions of genes as well as large chromosomal regions, gene insertions, introduction of single-nucleotide mutations within different gene loci, or chromosome splitting. Moreover, also genetic engineering of diploid and polyploid industrial *S. cerevisiae* strains has been greatly facilitated (Table 2).

2.2.1. Marker-less modifications and multiplexing

The efficiency of homologous recombination stimulated by CRISPR-Cas9 can be extremely high even without selection for the integrated DNA (DiCarlo et al., 2013) and hence selection markers can often be omitted. No subsequent removal or recycling of the selection markers is required (Solis-Escalante et al., 2014; Solis-Escalante et al., 2013).

Multiplexing (multiple simultaneous manipulations) of the *S. cerevisiae* genome using CRISPR-Cas9 were demonstrated by several groups (Bao et al., 2015; Generoso et al., 2016; Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b; Mans et al., 2015; Ryan et al., 2014; Ryan and Cate, 2014). The use of the CRISPR-Cas9 system for a simultaneous disruption of three genes in *S. cerevisiae* was first shown by (Bao et al., 2015), followed by a simultaneous deletion of six genes within a single transformation step (Mans et al., 2015), and works reporting an introduction of whole biosynthetic pathways into *S. cerevisiae* genome (Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b). An approach of combined multiplexed gene deletions and integrations was also demonstrated (Mans et al., 2015). The genes *ACS1* and *ACS2* were deleted simultaneously, using an integration cassette for the deletion of *ACS2* and a homology repair fragment for the deletion of *ACS1*. The integration cassette carried sequences coding for an *E. faecalis* pyruvate dehydrogenase complex consisting of six genes that were delivered as six fragments with flanking ends enabling homologous recombination of the neighbouring fragments. The first and the last fragments were homologous to up-and-downstream regions of *ACS2* (Mans et al., 2015). Recently, another promising approach for multiplexed genome editing has been reported, relying on improved RNA processing applying a bacterial endoribonuclease (Csy4 from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) (Ferreira et al., 2017b). Thereby a single transcript could be split into multiple gRNAs enabling for example a quadruple deletion at 96% efficiency. For the simultaneous editing of genes with similar sequences (e.g. isoenzymes/paralogs) off-targeting effects of 'promiscuous' guide-RNAs have been successfully applied (Ferreira et al., 2017a).

2.2.2. Point mutations

The CRISPR-Cas9 system has also been shown to facilitate introduction of point mutations into the *S. cerevisiae* genome (Biot-Pelletier and Martin, 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Laughery et al., 2015; Mans et al., 2015). The introduction of point mutations into the *S. cerevisiae* genome was used to prepare a mutant strain with decreased cellular accumulation of reactive oxygen species (Biot-Pelletier and Martin, 2016) or to study synergistic effects of different alleles after a simultaneous introduction of one deletion and four point mutations (Horwitz et al., 2015). When using CRISPR-Cas9 for the introduction of specific single-nucleotide mutations, it is necessary to prevent Cas9 from the repeated cutting of the first homology directed repair (even if the single nucleotide mutated is in the 20 bp gRNA binding region, Cas9 can tolerate such mismatches (Anderson et al., 2015; Fu et al., 2016; Hsu et al., 2013) and cleave the region repeatedly). Repeated cleavage by Cas9 can be avoided by introduction of an additional silent or synonymous change to the nucleotide sequence surrounding the point mutation (DiCarlo et al., 2013; Horwitz et al., 2015; Jakociunas et al., 2015b; Laughery et al., 2015), so that the gRNA target site or the PAM sequence is eliminated and the site cannot be cleaved by the Cas9 again. Mans et al. used, two repair oligonucleotide fragments to simultaneously introduce a single-nucleotide mutation into two different

genome sites, but not to disrupt the respective gRNA target sites, nor the PAMs (Mans et al., 2015). Out of eight transformants tested for the presence of the desired mutation, four contained both single-nucleotide changes. However, within these four transformants, two contained also additional undesired mutations, indicating that another run of Cas9 cleavage occurred. The efficiency of the desired modification was hence 25%. The disruption of the gRNA target site or the PAM sequence can protect the altered site from additional modifications, but on the other hand, it is not a seamless intervention.

A two-step strategy enabling a seamless introduction of point mutations, i.e. with no additional mutations needed (Fig. 4), was suggested by (Mans et al., 2015) and applied by (Biot-Pelletier and Martin, 2016). Within the first step, the Cas9 recognition site, and thus the risk of the repeated cutting, was eliminated by insertion of a 20 nucleotide heterologous stuffer sequence into the site of the double-strand break via a homologous repair fragment. In the second step, this stuffer took over the role of a recognition sequence, for which a second gRNA was needed. After cutting the DNA, the original guide RNA targeted sequence was brought back with a homologous recombination repair, thus seamlessly introducing the desired point mutation, and again preventing Cas9 from repeated cutting (Fig. 4). The exchange of the recognition sequence can be easily detected by PCR. However, because the introduction of the stuffer sequence means a transient disruption of the particular gene, the design of the stuffer is a subject to improvement when essential genes are targeted. The insertion of the stuffer sequence into a coding region of essential genes was shown to result in hampered cell growth and decreased viability.

Another tool for seamless nucleotide substitutions combines the CRISPR-Cas9 system and AID (activation-induced deoxycytidine deaminase) into the Target-AID tool (Nishida et al., 2016). The AID is an important component of the vertebrate adaptive immune system, as it generates antibody diversity by hypermutating the variable region of immunoglobulin genes. Namely, the AID is responsible for a deamination of deoxycytidine on a ssDNA (Muramatsu et al., 2000). Employing the CRISPR-Cas9 system, the deamination caused by the AID can be targeted to a region of interest. The Cas9-gRNA complex forms an

ssDNA region in the targeted DNA, since an RNA/ssDNA hybrid (R-loop) is formed (Chaudhuri et al., 2003), and targets the AID to this ssDNA region at the same time. A fusion protein consisting of a Cas9 variant (dCas9 or nCas9) and an AID ortholog PmCDA1 was targeted by a specific gRNA to *CAN1* or *ADE1* locus (Nishida et al., 2016). Whereas the single nuclease Cas9 induced deletions and insertions, the fusion proteins dCas9-PmCDA1 or nCas9-PmCDA1 induced point mutations (C → G or C → T). However, it was shown that the PmCDA1 expression leads to genome wide mutations in *S. cerevisiae* (Nishida et al., 2016; Rogozin et al., 2007).

2.2.3. Gene drives

Gene drives are genetic elements allowing the propagation of genes by non-Mendelian inheritance (Gantz and Bier, 2015). Thereby populations of organisms may be altered by inheritance of a certain genetic trait via sexual reproduction. Introducing such permanent alterations has been considered to prevent the spread of insect-transmitted diseases, to eliminate pesticide and herbicide resistance and to improve crops (Esvelt et al., 2014). Gene drives hold also in yeasts (DiCarlo et al., 2015) great promise for biotechnological applications or could be applied as possible countermeasure against pathogenic yeast species.

Different types of gene drives increasing the likelihood of inheriting a specific genetic trait by different mechanisms, have been reviewed by (Esvelt et al., 2014). Early designs of gene drives relied on homing endonuclease genes (Burt and Koufopanou, 2004). These endonucleases cut the corresponding locus of the chromosome that is lacking them, and within the repair, the endonuclease gene is copied into the damaged chromosome. Other gene drives are transposons that can copy and insert themselves into other genomic sites (Charlesworth and Langley, 1989), segregation distorters that destroy the second chromosome during meiosis (Lyttle, 1991), or Medea elements that express toxins killing the progeny that did not inherit them (Beeman et al., 1992; Chen et al., 2007). Also intracellular parasites that only allow the offspring of two infected parents to survive can be considered gene drives (Werren, 1997). Also CRISPR-Cas9 was used to create efficient gene drives in different organisms (Gantz and Bier, 2015; Hammond et al., 2016).

Multiple CRISPR-Cas9 RNA-guided gene drive systems were tested in *S. cerevisiae* (DiCarlo et al., 2015). The CRISPR-Cas9 gene drive system was split into an episomal plasmid carrying *CAS9* and genome-inserted gRNA. The gRNA targeting the *ADE2* gene was inserted into the *ADE2* locus, creating a strain with disrupted *ADE2* gene and eliminated target site (*ade2::sgRNA*). These haploid strains were mated with a wild type strain (of the opposite mating type) having or lacking an episomal *CAS9*-expressing plasmid. The inheritance of the (un) functional allele was detected visually since *ADE2* colonies are cream coloured and *ade2* mutants are red. When the *CAS9* was expressed, more than 99% of the diploids were red *ade2* mutants, meaning that the inherited functional copy of *ADE2* was efficiently disrupted by the CRISPR-Cas9 system. When the Cas9 plasmid was absent, no mutants were detected as the gRNA itself lacks the gene drive function. The mated diploid strains were then further reproduced by sporulation, and the generated haploids were examined. The Cas9⁺ diploids yielded 4:0 ratio of red:cream haploids, whereas the Cas9⁻ diploids yielded 2:2 ratio of red:cream haploids (as expected from the classic Mendelian inheritance of recessive alleles).

This gene drive also allowed the insertion of genes together with the gRNA cassette. In an experiment similar to the *ADE2* alterations, *URA3* was inserted *in cis* with the *ade2::sgRNA* drive element. The final haploids (after mating with wild type haploid and sporulation) within the tetrad were all red and contained the *URA3* copy.

In addition, essential gene recoding was tested by inserting an *ABD1*-targeting gRNA along with an *ABD1* gene mutated at its 3'-end, into the *ABD1* locus. All the final haploids (after mating with wild type haploid and sporulation) contained the drive element and recoded *ABD1* locus at the same time.

Fig. 4. Seamless two-step stuffer-assisted introduction of point mutations (PMs) designed by (Biot-Pelletier and Martin, 2016). This strategy eliminates repeated DNA cutting by Cas9 after introducing a single nucleotide mutation. Repeated cleavage by Cas9 can occur when the targeted alteration insufficiently changes the gRNA recognition site and repeated cleavage can lead to the introduction of additional unintended modifications (Mans et al., 2015). In the first step, a 20-nucleotide target genome sequence close to the intended PM is replaced by a heterologous stuffer fragment via homologous recombination. In the second step, the stuffer fragment acts as the target sequence, is recognized by a second gRNA. The original sequence is inserted back via a homologous recombination repair fragment that introduces the desired point mutation. These two steps help to introduce a point mutation into a genome site seamlessly, i.e. with no additional modifications of the gRNA target site or the PAM sequence. A disruption of the gRNA target site or the PAM sequence prevents Cas9 from a repeated cutting.

The gene drive efficiency was also tested in different genetic backgrounds, *i.e.* by mating the *ADE2* drive-containing haploids with phylogenetically and phenotypically diverse wild type *S. cerevisiae* strains. The drive system was shown to be robust as the same results were obtained regardless of the *S. cerevisiae* strain. When the large *CAS9* gene was encoded *in cis* together with the gRNA cassette (and not on a separate plasmid), the gene drive function was not impeded. When *ADE2*-disrupting drive haploids were mated with *ADE2*-restoring drive haploids, *ADE2* function was restored with more than 99% efficiency in the diploids, and in all the subsequent haploids generated by sporulation.

2.2.4. Chromosome engineering

Large-scale deletions of non-essential genomic sequences (exceeding 30 kbp) were also demonstrated with the CRISPR-Cas9 system and could be applied in minimum genome research in *S. cerevisiae* (Hao et al., 2016). In this work, a 38 kbp chromosomal region was targeted simultaneously by two gRNAs that were expressed from the same vector (design by (Bao et al., 2015)). Within the 50 tested mutants, 5 underwent the deletion of the large chromosomal fragment between the remote target sites of the two gRNAs.

Furthermore, the higher homologous recombination frequency determined by CRISPR-Cas9 enabled a 200-fold increase of the efficiency of PCR-mediated chromosome splitting (PCS). The PCS chromosome engineering technology with the integrated CRISPR-Cas9 editing was named CRISPR-PCS (Sasano et al., 2016). The PCS is used to split a *S. cerevisiae* chromosome at any desired locus and to generate two novel functional chromosomes. The splitting step is based on homologous recombination after an induction of a double strand break of the chromosome. Two HR fragments, so called splitting modules, are provided, one of them carrying a telomere sequence, and the second carrying both telomere and centromere sequences (Sugiyama et al., 2009). Using CRISPR-Cas9, the length of the homology sequence of the splitting module could be reduced from originally 400 bp to 50 bp. CRISPR-PCS was shown to allow the generation of simultaneous triple splits within a single chromosome, and single splits on up to four different chromosomes simultaneously (Sasano et al., 2016). This method can be used as a breeding approach to create novel *S. cerevisiae* strains with specific traits, by introducing specific chromosome deletions or duplications. Splitting chromosomes could also be useful to prevent engineered yeast from outbreeding with wild isolates.

2.2.5. Engineering of diploid and polyploid *S. cerevisiae* strains

Haploid yeast strains have historically been preferred to diploid and polyploid strains, as genetic manipulations are considerably easier and mutations have only to be introduced once. However, diploid and polyploid yeast strains have some characteristics beneficial for industrial use, such as rapid sugar fermentation or higher tolerance of stress conditions (Hansen and Kielland-Brandt, 1996). With the use of CRISPR-Cas9, the genome editing of the diploid and polyploid strains has been recently radically enhanced (Generoso et al., 2016; Ryan and Cate, 2014; Stovicek et al., 2015b; Zhang et al., 2014), broadening their possible applications (Table 2). Using a multiplexed CRISPR (CRISPRm) system, the homozygous integration of multiple linear overlapping DNA molecules into the genome of a polyploid industrial *S. cerevisiae* strain ATCC4124 was reported (Ryan and Cate, 2014). The CRISPRm system was further adapted to establish a standardized engineering method for multiplexing in yeasts (Lee et al., 2015; Ryan et al., 2014). A simultaneous gene disruption with knock-in (donor cassette used as a repair template for homologous recombination) was performed in diploid *S. cerevisiae* strains CBS7960, CLIB382 and Ethanol Red (Stovicek et al., 2015b). Another drawback of polyploid *S. cerevisiae* strains was the unavailability of auxotrophic strains. This limitation was overcome by (Zhang et al., 2014), who generated a quadruple auxotrophic mutant of the industrial polyploid strain ATCC4124. CRISPR-Cas9 was used for disruption of the four most popular marker genes *URA3*, *TRP1*, *LEU2* and *HIS3*. For the initial selection of *CAS9* and gRNA expression,

antibiotic (nourseothricin and hygromycin) resistance markers were used. While stress tolerance and thermotolerance of the strain ATCC4124 were not affected by the disruptions, the rate of sugar metabolism in the mutant strain was lower than in the parent strain. After transformation of the quadruple auxotrophic mutant by four complementing plasmids, the rate of sugar metabolism was significantly increased, though still lower than in the parental strain.

In another polyploid strain (Ethanol Red), single CRISPR-Cas9 mediated deletions (*ILV1*, *LEU4/9*) were performed with very high efficiency (~98%), but no transformants were obtained when offering two gRNAs simultaneously, probably due to a low transformation efficiency of the strain (Generoso et al., 2016). CRISPR-Cas9 has also been successfully adapted to accelerate linkage and association studies, that require the mapping of genomic regions influencing phenotypic variation (Sadhu et al., 2016). Conventional methods are hampered by recombination frequencies and resolving this issue with CRISPR-Cas9 enabled high resolution mapping of single polymorphisms causing phenotypical differences.

2.3. Toolbox of advanced CRISPR-Cas9 related applications in *S. cerevisiae*

Besides genome editing, CRISPR-Cas9 was also applied to the regulation of transcription (Section 2.3.1), optimization of gene expression (2.3.2) and metabolic engineering (2.3.3) in *S. cerevisiae*, as well as for manipulation of the genomes of other microorganisms within *S. cerevisiae* cells (2.3.4, Table 3). These advanced applications are described below and summarized in Table 3.

2.3.1. *crisprTFs*: activation/repression of transcription

The use of CRISPR-Cas9 for regulation of gene transcription is based on an endonuclease-deficient Cas9 variant (dCas9). This catalytically inactive version of Cas9 can be targeted by gRNA to a promoter, where it sterically blocks RNA polymerase binding (Fig. 5A) or elongation (Fig. 5B), resulting in transcriptional repression. This application was shown in human cells (Qi et al., 2013) and is called CRISPRi (CRISPR interference, in analogy to RNA interference, RNAi). In *S. cerevisiae*, dCas9 itself was initially also shown to act as a repressor of transcription (18-fold decrease of reporter gene expression) and a fusion to a repressor domain (Fig. 5C) showed even more stringent regulation (53-fold repression of the reporter gene) (Gilbert et al., 2013). Fusion proteins consisting of dCas9 and different transcriptional effector domains (activator, repressor, epigenetic effector) are also referred as CRISPR-based transcription factors, *crisprTFs* (Farzadfard et al., 2013), and can basically target the effector of interest to any locus (or multiple loci) by specific gRNA(s) (Fig. 5C).

Alternatively, a CRISPR-based system for transcription regulation has been introduced, in which the activation or repression of transcription is determined by a scaffold RNA (scRNA) and a separate effector protein instead of dCas9 fusions (Zalatan et al., 2015) (Fig. 5D). In contrast to *crisprTFs*, the transcriptional effector domains are not fused to dCas9, but rather linked via scRNA. scRNAs are engineered gRNAs, which contain additional sequences recognized by different RNA-binding proteins. The RNA-binding proteins are fused to transcription regulatory domains (for activation and repression) (Zalatan et al., 2015). Thereby it is possible to simultaneously activate and repress transcription of different genes. Multiplexing is enabled by co-expressing dCas9 and a set of scRNAs and transcription regulating domains. The system with a constitutively expressed scRNA was shown to permit slightly lower quantitative changes in transcription regulation than the dCas9 fusions proteins (Jensen et al., 2017) (see Table 3). However, the scRNA system provides unprecedented flexibility (simultaneous activation/repression) over the *crisprTF* fusion proteins.

Both systems (dCas9 fusions or scRNA assembling with transcription regulatory domains) were used to activate or repress transcription for different applications (Farzadfard et al., 2013; Gilbert et al., 2013; Jensen et al., 2017; Khakhar et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2016). Metabolic

Fig. 5. Different strategies for transcription regulation by an endonuclease-deficient Cas9 (dCas9) variant. (A) dCas9 is targeted by a gRNA to a promoter region, where it blocks the transcription initiation by preventing an RNA polymerase and transcription factors (TFs) from binding to the promoter. As a result, the transcription is repressed. (B) dCas9 is targeted by a gRNA to a coding region, where it sterically blocks RNA elongation. As a result, the transcription is repressed. (C) A transcription effector domain (TED) fused to dCas9 is targeted by a gRNA to a promoter region, where it either represses or activates the transcription. (D) Transcription effector domain (TED) is fused to an RNA-binding protein, which assembles with the scaffold RNA (scRNA) (Zalatan et al., 2015). Expressing dCas9 and multiple scRNAs, a simultaneous activation/repression of multiple promoters is possible (Zalatan et al., 2015).

fluxes in carotenoid or triacylglycerol biosynthetic pathway were redirected towards the product of interest (Jensen et al., 2017) and rate-limiting steps in metabolic pathways were identified (Deaner and Alper, 2017). crisprTFs also proved useful to map regulatory roles of distal and proximal elements in transcription (Gilbert et al., 2013). However, activation/repression appears to be influenced not only by the specific crisprTF used, but also by the promoter region targeted (Farzadfard et al., 2013). crisprTFs behaved either as an activator (targeting sequences upstream of the TATA box), or a repressor (targeting regions close to TATA box and transcription start site), meaning that the function of a single crisprTF (and possibly also scRNA based designs) can be programmed by the gRNA. For different promoters, no clear overall correlation was found between the level of transcriptional regulation and scRNA positioning in terms of the distance from the transcription start site as well as nucleosome occupancy. The correlation might have not been found due to the fact that S288C genome data were used for the scRNA positioning prediction, while the experimental work was performed in a CEN.PK strain (Jensen et al., 2017).

The approach of targeting dCas9 fused to a repressor (Mxi1) or an activator (VP64-p65-Rta, VPR) by gRNAs to different sites within promoter (*CYC1*, *NDE1*, *GPD1*) was used to generate graded gene expression ranging from near complete repression to overexpression. A set of gRNAs was used to gradually slide the binding position of repressing dCas9-Mxi1 or the activating dCas9-VPR towards relative to the TATA box. By a stepwise targeting of genes involved in a glycerol fermentation, pentose phosphate pathway or xylose catabolism, the relationship between the glycerol production, 3-dehydroshikimate production or specific growth rate on xylose respectively, and the gene's graded expression was defined (Deaner and Alper, 2017). This STEPS (Systematically Test Enzyme Perturbation sensitivities) approach thus allows to identify bottlenecks in metabolic pathways and to predict their optimization in terms of the level of gene expression (Deaner and Alper, 2017). In addition, tuneable synthetic promoters can also be designed by inserting multiple artificial gRNA-binding sites (operators) upstream of the promoter (Farzadfard et al., 2013). The possibility of enhanced modulation of gene transcription in *S. cerevisiae* was further used to establish an orthogonal, modular and tuneable cell-cell communication framework for yeast (Khakhar et al., 2016) or to study a strain's sensitivity to small drug molecules after repression of promoters of twenty different genes essential for viability (Smith et al., 2016).

In contrast to active Cas9, dCAS9 was expressed in *S. cerevisiae* from both inducible (Farzadfard et al., 2013; Khakhar et al., 2016) and strong constitutive (Gilbert et al., 2013; Jensen et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016) promoters, with no reported negative effects on the strain's physiology.

2.3.2. Optimization of heterologous gene expression

The CRISPR-Cas9 technology was used to build a toolkit for rapid and easy strain engineering of *S. cerevisiae* (Reider Apel et al., 2017). This toolkit includes 37 promoters, 10 protein tags, and Cas9-sgRNA plasmids targeting 23 different integration loci. Heterologous gene expression can thus be optimized examining different promoters, integration sites, growth phases and media, and protein tags determining product localization, solubility and stability. The authors also created a CASdesigner webtool, which facilitates to design the primers needed for the construction of the integration cassettes. The utilization of the toolkit was demonstrated by improvement of taxadiene synthase expression, which resulted in a 25-fold increase of the taxadiene production (Reider Apel et al., 2017).

2.3.3. Metabolic engineering applications

For industrial metabolic engineering applications, genomic integration is preferred to non-integrative plasmids, which may be unstable and demand selection pressure (Da Silva and Srikrishnan, 2012; Karim et al., 2013). The use of CRISPR-Cas9 for the integration of multigene biosynthetic pathways (up to 24 kbp) into the *S. cerevisiae* genome was shown by several authors: strains producing (R,R)-2,3-butanediol (BDO) from xylose (Shi et al., 2016), muconic acid (Horwitz et al., 2015), β -carotene (Jakociunas et al., 2015a; Ronda et al., 2015) or *n*-butanol (Lian et al., 2016), or a xylose-utilizing strain (Tsai et al., 2015) were generated. Using CRISPR-Cas9, considerable increases of mevalonate concentration (up to 41.5-fold) (Jakociunas et al., 2015b) or *p*-coumaric acid titer (4-fold) (Jakociunas et al., 2015a) were reached by engineering (gene knock-out and/or down-regulation) the mevalonate biosynthetic pathway or the tyrosine biosynthetic pathway, respectively. CRISPR-Cas9 was also used to knock-out the *CAR1* gene in *S. cerevisiae*, to reduce the formation of carcinogenic and genotoxic ethyl carbamate during ethanol fermentation (Chin et al., 2016). The *CAR1* gene coding for an arginase was knocked-out either by a complete deletion or by an introduction of a nonsense mutation. While the specific arginase activity was decreased by approximately 97% in both types of knock-out strains compared to the parental strains, their growth patterns, glucose consumption and ethanol production were similar to the parental strain. Moreover, also diploid industrial *S. cerevisiae* strains were successfully engineered to produce lactic acid (Stovicek et al., 2015b) or increased levels of 3-hydroxypropionic acid by improved biosynthesis of acetyl-CoA (Jessop-Fabre et al., 2016). The multiplex engineering may, however, lead to a reduction of fitness relative to the parent strain, caused for instance by a loss of some native biosynthetic capacity (Horwitz et al., 2015). Also a multi-faceted system suitable for combinatorial metabolic engineering relying on transcriptional activation, transcriptional interference, and gene deletion (CRISPR-AID) has recently been reported (Lian et al., 2017).

2.3.4. Manipulation of bacterial genomes

Cas9-directed cleavage alongside the high efficiency of homologous recombination in *S. cerevisiae* also helped to engineer bacterial genomes: *S. cerevisiae* cells expressing the components of the CRISPR-Cas9 system were used as a factory for engineering genomes of species, for which no efficient gene-editing tools were available (Kang et al., 2016; Tsarpopoulos et al., 2016). A method called mCRISTAR (multiplexed CRISPR-Cas9 in combination with transformation-associated recombination [TAR]) can be used for systematic studies of bacterial biosynthetic pathways that are silenced under laboratory conditions, but which could be a source of valuable bioactive metabolites (Kang et al., 2016). A way to activate such silenced biosynthetic pathway is to

Table 4
Design and molecular parts of CRISPR-Cas9 vectors in (non-)conventional yeasts.

Organism	Cassette for CAS9 ^g /gRNA (regulation of promoter)	Strategy	Reference
<i>S. pombe</i> (haploid)	<i>P_{ADHI}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong, constitutive)	Single-plasmid system: Episomal plasmid (ARS1) bearing the gRNA and the CAS9 expression cassettes; Co-transformation of donor fragment Two plasmid system: Integration of CAS9 expression vector in the genome; Transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with gRNA expression vector (and donor fragment)	Jacobs et al. (2014) Fernandez and Berro (2016)
	<i>P_{RRK1}</i> – rrk1 leader – gRNA – HH ribozyme		
<i>P. pastoris</i> (haploid)	<i>P_{HTA1}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>DAS1TT</i> (strong, constitutive)	Single episomal plasmid (PARS1) bearing the gRNA and the CAS9 expression cassettes; Co-transformation of donor fragment	Weninger et al. (2016a)
	<i>P_{HTB1}</i> – HH ribozyme – gRNA-HDV ribozyme – <i>AOX1TT</i>		
<i>Y. lipolytica</i> (haploid)	<i>P_{UAS1BB-TEF(136)}</i> – YlCAS9 (strong, constitutive)	Single episomal plasmid (CEN) bearing the gRNA and the CAS9 expression cassettes	Schwartz et al. (2016)
	<i>P_{SCR1-ARNAGly}</i> – gRNA – polyT <i>P_{TEFIn}</i> – HsCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> <i>P_{TEFIn}</i> – HH ribozyme – gRNA-HDV ribozyme – <i>MIG1TT</i>		
<i>K. lactis</i> (haploid or diploid)	<i>P_{FBA1}</i> – ScCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong, constitutive)	Integration of CAS9 expression vector in the genome; Co-transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with an linear, episomal plasmid bearing gRNAs (2 μ , pKD1 element), and linear donor cassettes	Horwitz et al. (2015)
	<i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>SUP4TT</i>		
<i>C. albicans</i> (diploid, lacking meiotic phase)	<i>P_{ENO1}</i> – CaCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong, constitutive)	SOLO system: CAS9 and gRNA expression cassette on single integrative plasmid; Co-transformation of CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid and donor cassette; DUET system: Integration of CAS9 expression vector in the genome; Transformation of the CAS9 expression strain with gRNA expression vector and donor fragment; Co-transformation of linear vector bearing CAS9 and gRNA expression cassettes and donor fragment; Transient expression of CRISPR-Cas9 components and selection for donor cassette integration;	Vyas et al. (2015) Min et al. (2015)
	<i>P_{SNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>ENO1TT</i>		
<i>C. glabrata</i> (haploid)	<i>P_{ENO1}</i> – CaCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong, constitutive)	Integration of gRNA expression vector in the genome of <i>C. glabrata</i> ; Transformation of the gRNA expression strain with CAS9 expression vector (integration);	Enkler et al. (2016)
	<i>P_{ScTEF1}</i> – ScCAS9 – <i>CYC1TT</i> (strong, constitutive) <i>P_{ScSNR52}</i> – gRNA – <i>TYR2TT</i>		

^a Codon usage of CAS9: Hs - human codon optimized CAS9, Yl - *Y. lipolytica* codon optimized CAS9, Sc - *S. cerevisiae* codon optimized CAS9, Ca - *C. albicans* codon optimized CAS9.

replace the native promoter with a well-characterised promoter. Cas9 was targeted to cut a gene cluster (coding for tetarimycin, lazarimide or an aromatic polyketide) into distinct operons. Then the fragments were simultaneously reassembled using four synthetic promoter cassettes within a single round. A web application enabling the design of the mCRISTAR system was introduced by the authors (Kang et al., 2016). In another work, *S. cerevisiae* cells expressing CRISPR-Cas9 were used as machinery for seamless deletion of a glycerol-3-phosphate oxidase gene of a *Mycoplasma mycoides* genome, which was maintained in *S. cerevisiae* cells as a circular extra-chromosome. Although the correct modification was only found in 20% of the screened clones (possibly because the PAM sequence within the target locus was maintained), this approach was still satisfactory since other methods for modifying the mycoplasma genome are considerably more time-and-labour intensive. The edited genome was then transplanted back into a Mycoplasma cell (Tsarmopoulou et al., 2016).

3. Yeast CRISPR-Cas9 systems beyond *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

The *S. cerevisiae* genome could be relatively easily manipulated for decades due to highly efficient HR machinery supporting recombination frequencies close to 100% with short (~50 bp) homology arms. CRISPR-Cas9 systems have even further extended these possibilities with simple marker-less and multiplexed modifications.

In contrast, considerably more effort was required to introduce targeted modifications in other yeasts due to the prevalent ectopic integration of homologous knockout cassettes and the ploidy of some yeast species such as *C. albicans* (see the integration frequencies of homology cassettes via of naturally occurring HR in Table 5). Especially in organisms with low HR frequencies, efficient genome modification tools such as CRISPR-Cas9 can greatly facilitate gene deletions and ease the generation of potent production strains (Gao et al., 2016; Min et al., 2015; Schwartz et al., 2016; Vyas et al., 2015; Weninger et al., 2016a).

The application of the CRISPR-Cas9 technology in *S. cerevisiae* systems (Bao et al., 2015; DiCarlo et al., 2013; Ryan and Cate, 2014) laid

the foundation for the implementation of CRISPR-Cas9 systems in *S. pombe*, the biotechnologically important yeasts *Y. lipolytica*, *P. pastoris*, *K. lactis* and the yeast pathogens *C. albicans* and *C. glabrata*. Although some elements such as the SV40 localization sequence for the nuclear import of Cas9 were applied universally, most factors needed species specific optimization (Table 4, Table 5) (Gao et al., 2016; Jacobs et al., 2014). Since little information on molecular tools such as RNAP III promoters or ARSs was available for several species, the successful implementation of CRISPR-Cas9 in non-conventional yeasts was accompanied by the development of innovative expression strategies, which are discussed below. Very recently, also CRISPR-Cas9 systems have been reported for *Saccharomyces pastorianus* (a hybrid of *S. cerevisiae* and *Saccharomyces eubayanus* commonly used for brewing) (de Vries et al., 2017), *S. cerevisiae* wine yeast strains (Vigentini et al., 2017) and the methylotrophic yeast *Ogataea polymorpha* (syn. *Hansenula polymorpha*) (Numamoto et al., 2017).

3.1. *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*

S. pombe is commonly used as uni-cellular model system resembling higher eukaryotes and for the heterologous production of mammalian proteins. This fission yeast resembles mammals more than other yeasts in terms of glycosylation, splicing and transcriptional regulation. In contrast to other fungal recombinant protein production hosts, many human proteins are well produced and strong promoters of mammalian viruses are recognized in *S. pombe* (Petrescu-Danila et al., 2009; Sambamurti, 1997).

Targeted genome modification efficiencies in *S. pombe* relying on the endogenous homologous recombination machinery mainly depend on the integration locus. Some loci can be targeted efficiently (75%–90% *URA4*, 87% *LEU1*, (Keeney and Boeke, 1994)), whereas for other loci the targeted integration of heterologous expression cassettes was not achieved at all or only at low efficiency (e.g. 5% *FIN1* (Fennessy et al., 2014)). The recombination frequency of homology cassettes could be increased by conventional means by engineering of the

Table 5
Genome editing applications and efficiencies of CRISPR-Cas9 in *S. pombe* and non-conventional yeasts.

Organism ^c	CAS9 + gRNA		CAS9 + gRNA + donor		CRISPR-Cas9 independent Achievable HR integration frequencies of homology cassettes in wildtype strains ^a	Reference
	Type of mutation	Targeting efficiency	Type of mutation	Targeting efficiency		
<i>S. pombe</i> (haploid)	NHEJ : small insertion and deletions at the cleavage point	<i>ADE6</i> n.d. <i>PIL1</i> 33% <i>ADE6</i> > 50%	HR HR	<i>ADE6</i> HR: 85–90% <i>ADE6</i> HR: 85–95%	Keeney and Boeke (1994): <i>URA4</i> , > 500 bp, 75%–90%; <i>LEU1</i> , > 500 bp, 87%	Jacobs et al. (2014) Fernandez and Berro (2016)
<i>P. pastoris</i> (haploid)	NHEJ: Single bp deleted upstream of Cas9 cleavage position (> 90% of transformants)	<i>GUT1</i> 94% ^b <i>AOX1</i> 95% <i>MPP1</i> 95% <i>TRM1</i> 94% <i>MXR1</i> 43% <i>OCH1</i> 51% <i>AOX1</i> + <i>GUT1</i> 69%	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> NHEJ and HR Predominantly NHEJ	<i>GUT1</i> NHEJ: 56–86% HR: 0–24%	Näätäsaari et al. (2012): < 0.1 to 30% depending on targeted gene and length of the homology arms	Weninger et al. (2016a)
<i>Y. lipolytica</i> (haploid)	NHEJ : small insertion and deletions at the cleavage point	<i>PEX10</i> 92% <i>KU70</i> 100% <i>MFE1</i> 90%	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> NHEJ and HR <u>$\Delta ku70$ strain:</u> HR	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> <i>MFE1</i> : NHEJ: 15%, HR: 73% <u>$\Delta ku70$ strain:</u> <i>MFE1</i> : HR: 100%	Wang et al. (1999): <i>POX1-POX5</i> : 50%, Fickers et al. (2003): <i>LIP2</i> 45%	Schwartz et al. (2016)
	NHEJ : small insertion and deletions at the cleavage point	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> 86–98% <i>PEX10</i> 62.5% <u>$\Delta ku70$ strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> 26% <u>$\Delta ku70/\Delta ku80$ strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> 0%	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> NHEJ and HR <u>$\Delta ku70/\Delta ku80$ strain:</u> HR	<u>Wildtype strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> : HR: 8%, NHEJ: 64% <u>$\Delta ku70$ strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> : HR:100% <u>$\Delta ku70/\Delta ku80$ strain:</u> <i>TRP1</i> : HR:100%	Verbeke et al. (2013): <i>ADE2</i> 2%	Gao et al. (2016)
<i>K. lactis</i> (haploid or diploid)	n.d.	n.d.	HR	<u>$\Delta ku80$ strain:</u> <i>ADH1</i> 43% <i>DIT1</i> 10% <i>NTD80</i> 20% <i>ADH1</i> + <i>DIT1</i> + <i>NTD80</i> 2%	Stark and Milner (1989): <i>TRP1</i> 11% Zeeman and Steensma (2003): <i>ACS1</i> 17% Kooistra et al. (2004): <i>ADE2</i> 88%) Krijger et al. (2012): <i>LAC4</i> 80% (Negredo et al., 1997): <i>ARG5,6</i> gene Single transformation to obtain homozygous mutant 10%	Horwitz et al. (2015)
<i>C. albicans</i> (diploid, lacking meiotic phase)	No positive transformants, co-transformation of donor obligatory	<i>ADE2</i> 0%	HR	<i>ADE2</i> 60–80% (SOLO system)		Vyas et al. (2015)
	No positive transformants, co-transformation of donor obligatory	<i>ADE2</i> 0%	HR	<i>ADE2</i> 20–40% (DUET system)		
<i>C. glabrata</i> (haploid)	n.d.	n.d.	HR	<i>ADE2</i> > 50% (both alleles), others integration in one allele		Min et al. (2015)
	NHEJ, most frequently large insertions NHEJ, most frequently insertion of a single bp	<i>ADE2</i> : n.d. <i>ADE2</i> : n.d.	n.d. HR	n.d. 3- to 8-fold increase in integration frequency of donor cassette	Cormack and Falkow (1999): <i>URA3</i> 200 bp HA: 90% Ueno et al. (2007): <i>ADE2</i> 200 bp HA: 20–50%	Enkler et al. (2016)

^a Wildtype strains do not contain mutations affecting recombination behavior (such as $\Delta ku70/\Delta ku80$ strains, these strains may show higher rates of HR).

^b For each gene three different gRNAs were tested [1], the highest targeting efficiency achieved is shown.

^c Vegetative state of most isolates.

expression vector (length, design of homology arms) and the transformation method (Grallert et al., 1993; Krawchuk and Wahls, 1999).

CRISPR-Cas9 systems for *S. pombe* combine high targeting efficiencies and reduced plasmid construction efforts compared to knockout/in cassettes. The first *S. pombe* CRISPR-Cas9 system was developed by the group of Zaratiegui (Jacobs et al., 2014), and fine-tuned by several research groups. Similar as performed for *S. cerevisiae* genome editing (DiCarlo et al., 2013), Jacobs et al. (2014) used a *CAS9* sequence codon optimized for the expression in human cells and a strong, constitutive promoter (*P_{ADH1}*) for *CAS9* expression. Due to a lack of well-defined *S. pombe* RNAP III promoters, an RNAP II promoter was used for the expression of the gRNA (Jacobs et al., 2014). In order to obtain 5' gRNA processing, the leader RNA from the *S. pombe* *RRK1* gene was added between the promoter and the gRNA sequence. In its natural context this leader RNA is cleaved off in the course of RNA maturation by an endogenous RNase in *S. pombe*, which was hijacked for gRNA expression. A ribozyme was placed downstream of the gRNA sequence to achieve correct 3' gRNA processing. This expression

strategy yielded correctly processed gRNAs lacking undesired bases at the 5' and 3' ends. The *ADE6* gene was selected as target locus to test the functionality of the system. Mutations in the *S. pombe* *ADE6* locus cause the accumulation of a red adenine precursor resulting in reddish coloring of the cells and a slow-growth phenotype. As initial expression strategy *CAS9* was integrated in the genome of *S. pombe* and this *CAS9* expression strain was transformed with different combinations of gRNA expression plasmids and PCR amplified donor cassettes (two-plasmid system). The targeting efficiencies for *ADE6* ranged from 50% to 98% and the highest efficiencies were obtained, when a donor fragment was co-transformed. Co-transforming a single plasmid bearing the gRNA and the *CAS9* expression cassettes (single-plasmid system), and the linear PCR amplified donor fragment yielded similar targeting efficiencies (85–90%).

Alternative selection markers for the expression of CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids in *S. pombe* were tested (Fernandez and Berro, 2016). A selection strategy based on the fluoride exporters *FEX1* and *FEX2* was developed. Deletion of *FEX1* and *FEX2* caused high sensitivity towards

fluoride compared to wildtype strains. Reconstitution of the wildtype phenotype rendered fluoride sensitive *S. pombe* $\Delta fex1/\Delta fex2$ strains fluoride resistant. In order to compare the *URA4* auxotrophy selection marker (Jacobs et al., 2014) and the *FEX1/FEX2* marker, CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids to target the *PIL1* gene were constructed. Using either the *URA4* or the *FEX1/FEX2* marker resulted in the same targeting efficiencies (33%), but the time for strain recovery was reduced by applying the *FEX1/FEX2* system. However, some drawbacks exist: Both marker systems are not applicable to *S. pombe* wildtype strains, but require a certain host strain genetic background ($\Delta fex1/\Delta fex2$, $\Delta ura4$). Moreover, the ARS plasmid curing, i.e. the elimination of the CRISPR-Cas9 system upon the introduction of the genomic modification, would result in impaired growth, i.e. a fluoride sensitive phenotype. In order to avoid these drawbacks, a CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid for antibiotic selection (Nourseothricin) was generated (Rodríguez-López et al., 2016), which allows plasmid curing and permits flexibility to engineer a broader range of *S. pombe* strains. Their plasmid is based on the CRISPR-Cas9 system developed by the group of Zaratiegui (Jacobs et al., 2014) with alteration for advanced cloning of the gRNAs (PCR-based cloning, removal of inefficient *CspCI* restriction site). Moreover, Rodríguez-López et al. (2016) developed an online tool “CRISPR4P” to design various primers required for the deletion of any region in the *S. pombe* genome. CRISP4P generates primers for gRNA cloning, construction of donor fragment and primers to verify the genome modification (Table 6). The donor fragments consist of 80 bp up- and downstream of the target sequence to be deleted and are joined together into a 160 bp fragment. Since proliferating *S. pombe* cells stay for the most of the time in the G2 phase with two genomic copies present (Lee and Nurse, 1988; Willis and Rhind, 2011), two copies of the target sequence have to be modified simultaneously and an unmodified copy can serve as a template for homologous repair. Therefore, it was suggested to trap the cells in the G1 phase by nitrogen starvation before making them competent for DNA transformation (Rodríguez-López et al., 2016). This treatment did not only increase the targeting efficiencies due to a reduced proportion of two-copy DNA containing cells, but also appeared to remodel the genome to increase the accessibility of genomic regions. Using this optimized CRISPR-Cas9 system, more than 80 non-coding RNA genes were deleted by co-transformation of a circular plasmid bearing *CAS9* and gRNA expression cassettes and a linear 160 bp donor fragment. The targeting efficiencies varied between the different genes, and the different gRNAs used for a single gene. For example, when deleting *SPNCRNA.745*, 5% positive colonies were obtained with one gRNA and 64% positive colonies with another gRNA.

3.2. *Pichia pastoris*

P. pastoris is the most commonly used eukaryotic expression host for the production of single heterologous proteins, surpassing even *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Bill, 2014). This methylotrophic yeast offers several advantages for the production of recombinant proteins such as secretion with low background from its own secretome, less extensive glycosylation compared to *S. cerevisiae* and growth to high cell density (Ahmad et al., 2014; Cregg et al., 2000; Vogl et al., 2013). HR targeting frequencies in *P. pastoris* are generally low and NHEJ is the preferred repair pathway. Depending on the gene locus and the size and design of the knockout cassettes the targeting rates range from < 0.1 to 30% (Näätsaari et al., 2012).

Recently, highly efficient gene targeting was achieved by using a CRISPR-Cas9 system (Weninger et al., 2016a). In contrast to *S. cerevisiae* and *S. pombe*, the development of an efficient CRISPR-Cas9 system proved to be difficult in *P. pastoris*. Weninger et al. systematically tested 95 combinations of different *CAS9* DNA sequences (various codon optimizations), gRNA sequences, RNAP III and RNAP II promoters in combination with ribozymes for the expression of the gRNAs, and RNAP II promoters for the expression of *CAS9*. There was a narrow range of optimal conditions for CRISPR-Cas9 functionality, as only a

Table 6
Web tools for the design of gRNAs targeting different yeast genomes.

Name	Reference yeast genomes	Primer/oligo design	Link	Reference
Yeaststriction webtool	33 <i>S. cerevisiae</i> genomes (http://www.yeastgenome.org/)	Yes	http://yeaststriction.tmw.tudelft.nl	Mans et al. (2015)
CHOPCHOP	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> , <i>P. pastoris</i>	Yes	https://chopchop.rc.fas.harvard.edu/	Montague et al. (2014)
CHOPCHOPv2	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> , <i>P. pastoris</i> , <i>C. albicans</i> , <i>Candida glabrata</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i>	Yes	http://chopchop.cbu.uib.no/	Labun et al. (2016)
CRISPR Toolset	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	Yes	http://wyrickbioinfo2.smb.wsu.edu/crispr.html	Laughery et al. (2015)
Yeast CRISPRi	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	No	http://ip2.github.io/yeast-crispri/	Smith et al. (2016)
CRISPy	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	No	http://staff.biosustain.dtu.dk/laeb/crispy_cempk/	Rontta et al. (2014)
CRISPR direct	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> , <i>S. pombe</i> , <i>Y. lipolytica</i> , <i>K. lactis</i> , <i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> , <i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i> , <i>Rhodotorula toruloides</i>	No	http://crispr.dbcls.jp/	Naito et al. (2015)
E-CRISPR	<i>S. cerevisiae</i> , <i>S. pombe</i> , <i>P. pastoris</i>	No	http://www.e-crisp.org/E-CRISPR	Heigwer et al. (2014)
CRISPR gRNA Design tool – ATUM	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	No	https://www.atum.bio/eCommerce/cas9/input	-
CRISPR-ERA: a comprehensive designer tool for CRISPR genome editing, (gene) repression, and activation	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	No	http://crispr-era.stanford.edu/	-
CRISPR4P gRNA design tool	<i>S. pombe</i>	Yes	https://github.com/Bahler-Lab/crispr4p	Rodríguez-López et al. (2016)
Computationally designed gRNAs to target 6341 genes in the <i>C. albicans</i> genome ^a	<i>C. albicans</i>	No	http://advances.sciencemag.org/content/suppl/2015/03/31/1.3.e1500248.DCI	Vyas et al. (2015)

^a Of those gRNAs > 500,000 target direct cleavage at both alleles, whereas 60,000 target only one of the two alleles.

few constructs enabled efficient genome editing (6 out of 95). The most efficient CRISPR-Cas9 system consisted of the human codon optimized CAS9 (DiCarlo et al., 2013) for *S. cerevisiae* under the control of a strong, constitutive promoter (P_{HTA1}) and ribozyme flanked gRNA expression under the control of a strong, constitutive RNAP II promoter (P_{HTB1}). The gRNA and the CAS9 expression cassettes were cloned on an ARS plasmid (PARS1). The feasibility of the system was evaluated by using the *GUT1* (glycerol utilization 1) gene as target locus. *GUT1* deficient transformants display a reduced growth phenotype on minimal media containing glycerol as sole carbon source. Upon transforming the CRISPR-Cas9 expression plasmid bearing the gRNA and the CAS9 expression cassettes, the targeting efficiencies varied between 83 to 94% depending on the variable gRNA sequence targeting *GUT1*. Several approaches were unsuccessful, including gRNA expression under the control of RNAP III promoters (lacking ribozymes), the expression of CAS9 and the gRNA from methanol inducible promoters, as well as the use of the streptococcal CAS9 sequence (Jinek et al., 2012) and a CAS9 DNA sequence optimized for *P. pastoris* codon usage. In addition to the *GUT1* locus, five different genes (*AOX1*, *MXR1*, *TRM1*, *MPP1* and *OCH1*) were targeted. Efficiencies for *AOX1*, *MPP1* and *TRM1* approached 100% for the best gRNA, although some gRNAs were not functional at all. *MXR1* and *OCH1* targeting efficiencies of approximately 50% were obtained with the best gRNA. The simultaneous mutation of two genes ('multiplexing', *AOX1* and *GUT1*) by transforming a CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid bearing two gRNA expression cassettes yielded targeting efficiencies of 18% - 69%, depending on the gRNA combinations used. The aforementioned experiments were performed without a donor fragment, relying solely on indels resulting during NHEJ mediated repair. When co-transforming a linear donor cassette and the circular CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid to target *GUT1* most of the transformants did not integrate the donor cassette, but displayed NHEJ mediated mutations. Hence due to the efficient ligation of DNA ends by the NHEJ mechanism, the targeted integration of homologous DNA cassettes still remained challenging in *P. pastoris*, possibly owing to rather inefficient HR repair mechanisms reported in this yeast (Näätsaari et al., 2012). However, this issue was recently resolved by applying a *ku70* deletion strain as host in order to reduce this counteracting NHEJ mechanism (Weninger et al., 2017). Flanking homologous ends of 1000 bp bases were sufficient for efficient, marker-less targeted integration using *P. pastoris* $\Delta ku70$. By providing the donor DNA on episomal plasmids in order to extend the availability of this donor DNA enhanced the integration efficiency also in wildtype strains (50% HR efficiency of marker-less cassettes) (Weninger et al., 2017). In general, repair of *ku70* deletions may be required in yeasts to ensure long-term genome stability, although in *P. pastoris* also *ku70* deletion strains appeared sufficient for typical protein production applications (Krainer et al., 2013).

3.3. *Yarrowia lipolytica*

Y. lipolytica is prominently used in industrial biotechnology due to its uncommon physiological characteristics including the ability to metabolize organic acids, polyalcohols and paraffins as sole carbon source (Blazeck et al., 2015; Ledesma-Amaro et al., 2016a, 2016b; Ledesma-Amaro and Nicaud, 2016a; Liu et al., 2015; Qiao et al., 2017; Shaw et al., 2016). *Y. lipolytica* has been applied for the production of proteins for food products, organic acids such as citric acid, polyalcohols, emulsifiers and surfactants as well as lipids and lipid derived compounds (Barth and Gaillardin, 1996; Ledesma-Amaro and Nicaud, 2016b). Recently, glycoengineered strains producing human therapeutic proteins were also reported (Tiels et al., 2012).

Strain engineering has been cumbersome in *Y. lipolytica*, due to the preferred ectopic integration of homology cassettes. HR occurs at low to moderate rates (50% *POX1-POX5*, *LIP2* 45%, *ADE2* 2%) if the length of the homology arms exceed 0.5–1 kbp, and can be influenced by the transformation protocol used (Fickers et al., 2003; Verbeke et al., 2013;

Wang et al., 1999). Two CRISPR-Cas9 systems based on different expression strategies have been reported for *Y. lipolytica* for rapid gene disruption (Gao et al., 2016; Schwartz et al., 2016).

(Schwartz et al., 2016) expressed CAS9, codon optimized for *Y. lipolytica*, under the control of the strong, constitutive, synthetic UAS1B8-TEF(136) promoter developed by another group (Blazeck et al., 2011). For the expression of gRNAs, synthetic hybrid promoters were used. These promoters were based on non-coding RNA (ncRNA) promoters and t-RNA promoters, both recognized by RNAP III. These synthetic promoters were compared to naturally occurring RNAP III promoters. The CAS9 and the gRNA expression cassette were cloned on a single episomal plasmid (pCRISPRyl). *PEX10* was selected as target gene for the implementation. In contrast to wildtype *Y. lipolytica* strains, *PEX10* deficient strains are unable to metabolize long chain fatty acids and display a slow growth phenotype in media containing oleic acid as sole carbon source. *PEX10* targeting efficiencies ranged between 30% for the natural *SNR52* promoter and up to 92% for the synthetic promoter variant SCR1'-tRNA^{Gly}. All synthetic promoters outperformed the natural variants tested. Interestingly, ribozyme flanked gRNA expression under the control of an RNAP II promoter, as used in *S. cerevisiae* (Gao and Zhao, 2014), *P. pastoris* (Weninger et al., 2016a) and the *Y. lipolytica* CRISPR-Cas9 system (Gao et al., 2016), was less successful compared to RNAP III promoter based expression.

The *PEX10* targeting efficiency could further be increased from 52% to 92% by adapting the selection procedures (by increasing the outgrowth period on selective liquid media from two to four days before plating on non-selective agar plates). The requirement for a long outgrowth period might indicate that further optimization might yield transformation efficiencies approaching 100%, even if the outgrowth period is reduced/omitted. Similarly as shown for *PEX10*, targeting the genes, *KU70* and *MFE1* (two days outgrowth), resulted in disruption frequencies of 100% and 90%.

When a linear *MFE1* homology donor fragment was co-transformed with the episomal CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid, 73% of the transformants integrated the donor cassette in the *MFE1* locus, 15% contained NHEJ-mediated mutations and 12% did not contain a mutation in the target locus. Transforming solely the donor cassette, bearing a Hygromycin resistance cassette for selection as control, did not yield any transformants, which integrated the donor cassette at the target locus.

Co-transforming a $\Delta ku70$ strain with the CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid and the donor cassette yielded a 100% correct integration frequency of the donor cassette. The Ku70 protein is involved in NHEJ, hence Ku70 deficient strains predominantly repair DNA damage by HR (Näätsaari et al., 2012; Verbeke et al., 2013). The CRISPR-Cas9 system developed by Schwartz et al. (2016), was successfully applied (Rodriguez et al., 2016) to identify two genes, *XDH* and *XKS*, essential for the xylitol metabolism. Another CRISPR-Cas9 system setup (Schwartz et al., 2017) was applied to identify integration loci, which allow high level recombinant gene expression and where the integration event does not negatively affect cell viability. Therefore, CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids to target 17 different (pseudo-)genes and the corresponding homology donor cassettes were co-transformed. The donor sequence consisted of an eGFP expression cassette flanked by homology arms for integration and was provided on an episomal plasmid. Of the 17 loci tested, five loci (*AXP*, *XPR2*, *MFE1*, *A08* and *D17*) resulted in high, CRISPR-Cas9 mediated integration frequencies (48%–62%). Disruption at the integration sites did not hamper cell growth and the eGFP expression levels were similar except for the *MFE1* locus (~2.3-fold reduction compared to other loci). The insights on these integration loci were used for metabolic engineering applications by designing a plasmid family to integrate multiple genes in different loci. Five plasmid pairs consisting of the CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid and the corresponding donor plasmid for the marker-less integration of expression cassettes at the five identified loci were generated. These plasmids were applied for the integration of a lycopen biosynthesis pathway. This system is a valuable alternative to Cre-loxp based systems for sequential integration

and marker-recycling (Fickers et al., 2003) or multi-gene expression cassettes, which are prone to loop-out recombination and genetic instability (Zhu et al., 2009).

A second strategy for CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing in *Y. lipolytica* was developed (Gao et al., 2016). Gao et al. expressed a human codon optimized *CAS9* variant under the control of the strong, constitutive *TEF1in* promoter (Tai and Stephanopoulos, 2013) and the gRNA flanked by ribozymes also under the control of the *TEF1in* RNAP II promoter. The gRNA and the *CAS9* expression cassettes were cloned on a single episomal plasmid. The *TPR1* gene (essential for tryptophan biosynthesis) was selected as target locus for the implementation. Similar to another work (Schwartz et al., 2016), increasing the outgrowth/regeneration time after transformation increased the efficiencies (four days growth in liquid selective media: 86% compared to zero days: 12% and two days: 62%). Transforming a *ku70/ku80* double deletion strain or a *ku70* deletion strain with the CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids to introduce indel mutations and omitting outgrowth in liquid media did not result in positive transformants due to the increased toxicity of CRISPR-Cas9 in the NHEJ reduced strains. However, an outgrowth period of four days increased the targeting efficiency up to 26%. For the CRISPR-Cas9 mediated integration of homologous donor cassettes, two strategies were compared: Firstly, linear donor cassettes and the episomal CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid were co-transformed. As a second approach the donor sequence was provided on the episomal CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid. In the wildtype strain the integration of the donor cassette was low (11%), independently of how the donor was provided. For the $\Delta ku70$ and the $\Delta ku70/\Delta ku80$ strain the integration rate of the donor was 100%, when the donor fragment was provided on an episomal plasmid. However, the targeting efficiency decreased to 10%, when the linear donor had been co-transformed. It was assumed that the linear DNA was not sufficiently sustained in the cells and that episomal maintenance favors the HR frequency (Gao et al., 2016).

When performing multiplexing, the expression of several gRNAs from a single plasmid yielded higher transformation efficiencies (37% *TPR1* and *PEX10* double mutation frequency) compared to the co-transformation of two CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids (2%). A triple-disruption efficiency of 19% was obtained using a plasmid bearing three different gRNAs to target *TRP1*, *PEX10* and *GUT2*.

Although different molecular parts were applied for the two *Y. lipolytica* CRISPR-Cas9 systems, both allow highly efficient gene targeting. It might be interesting to combine the single features (e.g. using the *Y. lipolytica* codon optimized *CAS9* in combination with ribozyme-flanked gRNA expression (Gao et al., 2016)) to further improve gene targeting efficiencies. The *Y. lipolytica* CRISPR-Cas system has also been implemented as a BioBricks (TheBioBricksFoundation, 2012) compatible metabolic engineering toolkit termed ‘YaliBricks’ (Wong et al., 2017).

3.4. *Kluyveromyces lactis*

K. lactis was one of the first yeasts, for which a transformation system had been developed (Das and Hollenberg, 1982) and it serves as an expression platform for β -galactosidases used for the production of lactose-free dairy products (Rodicio and Heinisch, 2013; Spohner et al., 2016; Van Ooyen et al., 2006). In addition to the recombinant production of a vast range of industrially relevant proteins, *K. lactis* produces interesting native enzymes such as inulinase, phospholipase B and chitinase (Van Ooyen et al., 2006). Gene targeting efficiencies are low (11% *TRP1*, 17% *ACS1* (Stark and Milner, 1989; Zeeman and Steensma, 2003), but differ enormously depending on the integration locus and the design of the homology cassette, as for some genes higher efficiencies were achieved (*LAC4* 90%, *ADE2* 88%) (Kooistra et al., 2004; Krijger et al., 2012; Van Ooyen et al., 2006). The implementation of CRISPR-Cas9 in *K. lactis* was readily achieved: A *S. cerevisiae* optimized CRISPR-Cas9 system needed mild adaptations for the functional expression in *K. lactis* (Horwitz et al., 2015). *CAS9*, optimized for the

expression in *S. cerevisiae*, was expressed under the control of the strong, constitutive *FBA1* promoter, which is active in *S. cerevisiae* and *K. lactis*. The *CAS9* expression vector was integrated in the genome of *K. lactis*. The gRNA expression cassette was cloned on an episomal 2 μ plasmid from *S. cerevisiae*, which included the pKD1 stabilizing element for expression in *K. lactis*. The expression of the gRNA was driven by the *SNR52* polymerase III promoter and terminated by the *SUP4* terminator, as performed in *S. cerevisiae* (DiCarlo et al., 2013). A *K. lactis* $\Delta ku80$ *CAS9* expression strain was co-transformed with the 2 μ gRNA expression plasmid and marker-less linear donor cassettes. Using this system the marker-less integration of three donor cassettes to comprise a multi-enzyme pathway at three different genomic loci (*DIT1*, *ADH1*, and *NDT80*) was achieved in a single transformation event (2.1% triple integration efficiency) in the *K. lactis* $\Delta ku80$ strain.

3.5. *Candida albicans*

C. albicans is commonly found amongst the commensal microbiota colonizing the human gastrointestinal and genitourinary tract. However, it can cause severe infections (“candidiasis”) in immunocompromised individuals including transplant recipients, HIV and chemotherapy patients (Berman and Sudbery, 2002; Kabir et al., 2012; Kabir and Hussain, 2009; Mayer et al., 2017). *C. albicans* has a heterozygous diploid genome and there are no haploid strains available (Jones et al., 2004). Moreover, variations in the chromosome number are common and many strains contain one or more additional copies of a chromosome. Thus, genome manipulations and the characterization of mutations that affect its pathogenicity have been challenging (Selmecki et al., 2010; Selmecki et al., 2009).

A CRISPR-Cas9 system that allows highly efficient gene targeting in *C. albicans* was developed (Vyas et al., 2015). However, several species-specific obstacles had to be overcome: The leucine CUG codon, which is predominantly translated as serine in *C. albicans*, had to be altered in the *CAS9* coding sequence. Moreover, there were no ARSs and expression elements for small RNAs characterized in *C. albicans*. Thus two integrative expression systems termed SOLO and DUET were developed (Vyas et al., 2015): The SOLO expression vector bore the *CAS9* and the gRNA expression cassettes and was integrated in the genomic *ENO1* target locus. The strong, constitutive *ENO1* promoter was used for the expression of *CAS9*. The RNAP III promoter *SNR52* from *S. cerevisiae* was used for the expression of the gRNAs. *ADE2* was selected as target locus. *ADE2* deficient strains show a red phenotype, which can only be obtained if both alleles of the *ADE2* gene are simultaneously deleted in *C. albicans*.

Alternatively, the *CAS9* and the gRNA expression system were provided on different plasmids (DUET system), both of which contained the Nourseotricin selection marker. First, the cells were transformed with the *CAS9* expression vector, followed by marker recycling and the transformation of the *CAS9* expression strain with the gRNA expression vector and a linear donor fragment. Besides the increase in workload, the targeting efficiencies of the DUET system were reduced (20–40% for *ADE2*) compared to the SOLO system (60–80% for *ADE2*). Interestingly, it was necessary to co-transform a donor fragment to obtain $\Delta ade2$ mutants, whereas the absence of the donor fragment did not yield *ADE2* deficient colonies (Vyas et al., 2015). In addition to *ADE2*, four different genomic loci, *CDR1* and *CDR2* (two alleles each), were targeted with a single gRNA achieving 20% targeting efficiencies. The co-transformation of the SOLO *ADE2* targeting plasmid and the *CDR1/CDR2* targeting plasmid and the corresponding donor cassettes yielded strains with mutations in six different loci from a single transformation event. Moreover, a large set of gRNAs to target 6341 genes in the *C. albicans* genome was computationally designed (Vyas et al., 2015). Of those gRNAs, > 500,000 target both alleles, whereas 60,000 target only one of the two alleles.

A strategy for CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid curing in *C. albicans* was developed (Min et al., 2015). A linear CRISPR-Cas9 expression vector

(*CaCAS9* and gRNA, Nourseotricin selection marker) and linear donor cassettes (*ARG4* selection marker) were co-transformed and solely selected for transformants bearing the donor cassettes. *ADE2* was used as target locus. Co-transformation of the donor fragment and the linearized CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid produced red colonies at a high frequency. Interestingly, the CRISPR-Cas9 system was not integrated in the genome, but transiently expressed without an ARS. Similar results were also obtained, when *CAS9* and the gRNA were provided on separate vectors, the donor contained the Nourseotricin selection marker and selection on Nourseotricin containing media had been performed. To verify CRISPR-Cas9 mediated integration of the donor cassette, they co-transformed the *CAS9* expression cassette without the gRNA expression cassette and the donor fragment, and solely the donor fragment. Upon transformation, in both cases selection for the integration of the donor fragment did not result in *ade2Δ/ade2Δ* transformants. Integration of the donor fragment was also obtained, when the target site was located 0.9 kbp from the recombination site (9/10 red transformants). The transient expression offers many benefits such as the use of multiple gRNAs (libraries) with minimal cloning effort as well as a reduced off-targeting activity and toxicity.

3.6. *Candida glabrata*

C. glabrata is the second most common opportunistic fungal pathogen causing candidiasis after *C. albicans*. In contrast to the latter, *C. glabrata* is more resistant to antifungal treatment and is associated with a higher mortality rate (Fidel et al., 1999; Krcmery and Barnes, 2017). *C. glabrata* is a haploid yeast, phylogenetically closer related to *S. cerevisiae* than *C. albicans*. Efficient gene targeting relying on HR can be obtained with knockout cassettes containing 200 bp homology arms (*URA3* > 90%, *ADE2* 20–50%) (Cormack and Falkow, 1999; Ueno et al., 2007). However, the targeted integration of short (40–60 bp) homology sequences is inefficient in *C. glabrata*.

In order to expand the molecular toolbox for engineering *C. glabrata*, a CRISPR-Cas9 system was developed (Enkler et al., 2016). Two different designs were tested: In the first design, the same parts from the first *S. cerevisiae* CRISPR-Cas9 system (DiCarlo et al., 2013) were used (i.e. a human codon optimized *CAS9* under the control of the *S. cerevisiae* *TEF1* promoter and the gRNA under the control of the *S. cerevisiae* *SNR52* promoter). In a second design, endogenous promoters from *C. glabrata* were used: *CAS9* was expressed under the control of the weak endogenous *CYC1* promoter and the gRNA under the endogenous RNAP III *RNAH1* promoter followed by the tRNA *TYR2* terminator. In both systems, the gRNA and *CAS9* were provided on two different plasmids. The gRNA expression vector was transformed first, because a reduced growth phenotype was observed upon *CAS9* expression. Thereafter, the *CAS9* expression vector and, if desired, a homologous donor DNA were co-transformed. Both the *S. cerevisiae* and the *C. glabrata* optimized expression constructs enabled the functional production of Cas9 and the gRNA.

However, introducing NHEJ mutations upon the transformation of the expression vectors (*CAS9* and gRNA in combination with various promoters) caused different mutations at the target site (*ADE2* locus). When using the endogenous promoter, a single nucleotide was inserted at the Cas9 cutting site, whereas *CAS9* expression under the control of the *S. cerevisiae* *TEF1* promoter generated large insertions of nucleotides. Subsequently, the endogenous CRISPR-Cas9 system was tested for the integration of donor DNA in the *ADE2* locus. When using a short donor fragment (57 bp flanked by either 20 bp or 200 bp homology arms), the integration efficiency was increased 4-fold (20 bp homology arms) up to 8-fold (200 bp homology arms) compared to the control lacking the CRISPR-Cas9 system. When using a larger donor fragment (1202 bp flanked by either 20 bp or 200 bp homology arms) the targeting efficiency was increased 3-fold independently if 20 or 200 bp homology arms were used. This finding indicates that the size of the flanking regions is especially important for short donor fragments. As

first application of this CRISPR-Cas9 system, two genes (*YPS11* and *VPK1*) were deleted in *C. glabrata* and the virulence of the mutant strains was tested in *Drosophila melanogaster* infection. Very recently, also the performance of CRISPR-Cas9 system in *C. glabrata* wildtype and *lig4* (*Lig4p* is involved in NHEJ) deletions strains was compared, suggesting similar advantages to the use of CRISPR-Cas in NHEJ impaired strains in other yeasts (e.g. (Gao et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Weninger et al., 2017)).

4. Recommendations for the design of efficient CRISPR-Cas9 systems in yeast cells

The implementation of CRISPR-Cas9 in different yeasts needed a species-specific optimization. The most efficient designs for each species varied in part considerably to each other and to the 'reference' design in *S. cerevisiae*. Yet, some concepts proved universally relevant and the most critical factors influencing the efficiency of genome editing with the CRISPR-Cas9 are summarized herein.

- In *S. cerevisiae*, it appears favourable to express *CAS9* from a constitutive, weak to medium-strength promoter (Generoso et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Mans et al., 2015; Ryan and Cate, 2014; Sasano et al., 2016; Stovicek et al., 2015b). Inducible time-limited expression of *CAS9* may result in decreased targeting efficiency (Ronda et al., 2015) and expression of *CAS9* from strong promoters was shown to impair the fitness and growth of the strain (Generoso et al., 2016; Ryan and Cate, 2014). *CAS9* has most frequently been expressed from the *TEF1* promoter (Bao et al., 2015; DiCarlo et al., 2013; Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b; Mans et al., 2015; Ronda et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2016; Stovicek et al., 2015b). In yeast systems beyond *S. cerevisiae*, *CAS9* was most commonly expressed under the control of a strong constitutive promoter (Enkler et al., 2016; Fernandez and Berro, 2016; Gao et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Jacobs et al., 2014; Min et al., 2015; Schwartz et al., 2016; Vyas et al., 2015; Weninger et al., 2016a). Inducible expression had been tested for *P. pastoris* and was not successful (Weninger et al., 2016a). The promoter choice may also have an influence on the type of mutation introduced. In *C. glabrata* either single bp insertions or larger indels had been observed, when different promoters were used for the expression of *CAS9* (Enkler et al., 2016).
- Codon optimization of *CAS9* does not seem to be crucial in terms of the targeting efficiency in *S. cerevisiae* and most other yeasts. High targeting efficiency was shown in *S. cerevisiae* when using the natural *S. pyogenes* *CAS9* sequence (Bao et al., 2015; Ryan and Cate, 2014), as well as *S. cerevisiae* codon optimized (Generoso et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015) or human codon optimized *CAS9* (DiCarlo et al., 2013). In contrast, in *P. pastoris* the codon optimization of *CAS9* strongly affected targeting efficiency (Weninger et al., 2016a). The codon optimization of *CAS9* might also be required for yeasts with non-canonical codon assignments such as *C. albicans* (Vyas et al., 2015).
- In *S. cerevisiae*, gRNA is predominantly expressed as a chimeric single guide RNA from the *SNR52* promoter (DiCarlo et al., 2013; Generoso et al., 2016; Gilbert et al., 2013; Horwitz et al., 2015; Jakociunas et al., 2015a, 2015b; Jensen et al., 2017; Laughery et al., 2015; Mans et al., 2015; Ronda et al., 2015; Stovicek et al., 2015b), with two exceptions in terms of targeting efficiency. First, in polyploid a *S. cerevisiae* strain, higher efficiency was achieved when expressing gRNA from the tRNA^{Phe} promoter (Ryan and Cate, 2014). Second, using the CRISPR-Cas9 system for regulating of transcription (see Section 2.3.1), inducible expression of gRNA was beneficial due to the possibility to tightly control dCas9 targeting (Jensen et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016). In other yeast systems, the gRNA was either expressed by an RNAP III promoter (in most cases *P_{SNR52}*) (Enkler et al., 2016; Horwitz et al., 2015; Min et al., 2015; Schwartz et al., 2016; Vyas et al., 2015) or was flanked by ribozymes or

alternative processing elements and expressed under the control of a constitutive RNAP II promoter (Fernandez and Berro, 2016; Gao et al., 2016; Jacobs et al., 2014; Weninger et al., 2016a). The introduction of ribozymes complicates cloning efforts (Weninger et al., 2016a), hence rather RNAP III promoter should be tested first. If natural RNAP III promoters do not work, synthetic ones may be considered (Schwartz et al., 2016) or RNAP II promoters in combination with gRNAs flanked by processing elements.

- In all yeast species, attention must be paid to a careful choice of the gRNA binding site within the targeted genome region. It is advisable not to target telomere regions and regions with high nucleosome occupancy (Reider Apel et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2016). In addition, testing several gRNAs for the deletion of a single gene can be recommended in order to increase the success rate of such experiments. Some gRNAs might not be functional due to their secondary structure (Jakociunas et al., 2015a). Several *in silico* gRNA tools are available for assisting in the design (Table 6 and see the last bullet point).
- The use of an *in vitro* pre-assembled CRISPR-Cas9 plasmid for transformation of *S. cerevisiae* assures higher efficiency than the *in vivo* assembly of multiple fragments (multiple gRNA cassettes or multiple integration fragments), which may anneal incorrectly (e.g. (Jakociunas et al., 2015a)). For yeast species beyond *S. cerevisiae*, such approaches have not been tested yet.
- The choice of a two-component (DiCarlo et al., 2013; Stovicek et al., 2015b) or a single plasmid (Generoso et al., 2016; Ryan and Cate, 2014) CRISPR-Cas9 system does not seem to play a key role in the efficiency of the genome editing in *S. cerevisiae*. In *S. pombe* (Jacobs et al., 2014) and *C. albicans* (Vyas et al., 2015), the expression of CAS9 and the gRNA from single plasmid yielded higher targeting efficiencies, but there is an ongoing discussion how safe such applications are due to possible gene drives arising from a fully active genomically integrated CRISPR-Cas9 system (DiCarlo et al., 2015; Esvelt et al., 2014).
- Some yeasts might require extended out-growth periods after the transformation as shown for *Y. lipolytica* (Gao et al., 2016; Schwartz et al., 2016).
- The types of mutation, which can be introduced, differ among the yeast species. Mutations (transformation of plasmid(s) bearing CAS9 and gRNA) caused by mistakes during the NHEJ process could be introduced in all species described herein, except for *C. albicans*, for which the co-transformation of a donor fragment is obligatory. In case of co-transformations of the CRISPR-Cas9 system and donor cassettes most species integrated the donor fragment. Exceptions are *Y. lipolytica*, of which transformants bear mutations introduced by NHEJ or HR, and *P. pastoris*, where the NHEJ process is dominant (unless a NHEJ impaired $\Delta ku70$ strain is used or an ARS is placed on the donor fragment (Weninger et al., 2017)).
- Appendix A - Supplementary data of this review provides a concrete example highlighting key design steps to achieve gene deletion in yeast (including gRNA selection, considerations on ribozymes and design of a donor fragment).
- Several web tools for *in silico* design and selection of a gRNA sequence are available that determine a unique target site within the *S. cerevisiae* genome, as well as in the genomes of several non-conventional yeasts (Table 6 and also reviewed by (Stovicek et al., 2017)). The endonuclease Cas9 can be targeted by the gRNA basically to any genome site composed of an NGG sequence (protospacer adjacent motif, PAM) followed by a 20 nucleotide sequence that is complementary to the 5' end of the gRNA (Jinek et al., 2012). Since the recognition is based on complementarity, the design of the gRNA is critical to avoid any off-targeting effects, i.e. unintended cleavage at other sites in the genome. The web-based easy-to-use interfaces (Table 6) offer to either choose a targeted gene by its name or to insert a sequence of the targeted gene or region. Subsequently a list of possible gRNAs is generated. Off-targeting is prevented as a

BLAST search against a reference yeast genome is performed alongside the design process. Some of the web tools enable as well to design the primers for cloning of the gRNAs.

5. Conclusion & outlook

The comparison of innovative CRISPR-Cas9 expression strategies presented here may serve as guidelines to implement and refine CRISPR-Cas systems for highly efficient genome editing in yeasts as well as other eukaryotic organisms.

Despite the availability of different plasmids and expression strategies, it is not guaranteed that a certain CAS9/gRNA expression strategy, which enables efficient gene targeting in one species, will also function in another (Gao et al., 2016; Weninger et al., 2016a). In yeast, species-specific optimization led to the development of novel expression tools such as synthetic RNAP III promoters for *Y. lipolytica* and the *rrk1* leader processing to control the length of the transcription product in *S. pombe* (Jacobs et al., 2014; Schwartz et al., 2016). Interestingly, not only the expression features and molecular parts differ among yeast species, but also the way Cas9/gRNA induced strand breaks are repaired. In *C. albicans* the co-transformation of a homologous donor fragment is prerequisite to obtain deletion mutants (Vyas et al., 2015), whereas in *P. pastoris* Cas9/gRNA induced strand breaks are predominantly repaired by NHEJ, even if a donor fragment is provided (Weninger et al., 2016a). The CRISPR-Cas9 systems developed have the potential to generate markerless production strains and to replace long established techniques such as site specific recombinases (Cre/loxP, Flippase/FRT). However, CRISPR-Cas9 mediated HR repair may be improved in most of the yeast species. Systematical studies are necessary, which evaluate the length and design of the “ideal” donor cassette and how it should be delivered. Moreover, the transient expression as performed in *C. albicans* might be adapted to other yeast species to reduce the time for CRISPR-Cas9 curing and toxic off-targeting effects (Min et al., 2015).

The toolbox of advanced CRISPR-Cas9 related applications available in *S. cerevisiae* may also be adapted for other yeasts species: crispRTFs (Farzadfard et al., 2013) should for example be universally applicable tools for regulating transcription in any species, and large fragment deletions demonstrated in *S. cerevisiae* (Hao et al., 2016) may help to universally engineer minimal genomes. Also metabolic engineering in non-conventional yeasts will benefit from CRISPR-Cas9 fuelled applications demonstrated in *S. cerevisiae* (Table 3).

Efficient CRISPR-Cas9 systems may then also be used to study biotechnologically relevant biological processes such as the unfolded protein response relevant for protein secretion (as demonstrated in mammals (Adamson et al., 2016)). Also several other CRISPR-Cas innovations have so far only been applied to organisms such as bacteria and higher eukaryotes, these include: Cas9 variants showing reduced off-targeting (Carrington et al., 2015; Kleinstiver et al., 2016; Slaymaker et al., 2016; Zischewski et al., 2016), improved data analysis specificity (Lindsay et al., 2016), the understanding of structural mechanisms (Anders et al., 2016; Anders et al., 2014; Jinek et al., 2014; Sternberg et al., 2014) and novel RNA guided endonucleases, which may substitute Cas9 (e.g. Cpf1 (Burstein et al., 2016; Watkins-Chow et al., 2017; Zetsche et al., 2015)) or can target RNA (Abudayyeh et al., 2016). Yet these innovative approaches bear also in yeasts considerable potential for enhancing genome editing or as RNA-targeting tools. Additionally, novel gRNA processing strategies (Nowak et al., 2016) relying on native tRNA-processing systems (Xie et al., 2015) may help to improve multiplexing applications in yeasts.

Eventually, it may be interesting to establish a CRISPR-Cas9 toolbox that could be applied in different yeasts species relying on widely applicable parts. Recently promoters and ARSs have been reported that function in different yeast species (Liachko and Dunham, 2013; Portela et al., 2017; Zeevi et al., 2014). Using these universal molecular parts in combination with ribozymes may pave the way for multi-yeast CRISPR-Cas9 systems.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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